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Covariance of the Photometric IDT Signal Parameters

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1. INTRODUCTION

The IDT Preprocessing provides an estimate ($\hat{\underline{\beta}}$) of the IDT signal parameters vector $\underline{\beta} = (\beta_1 \ \beta_2 \ \beta_3 \ \beta_4 \ \beta_5)'$ from photon counts $\{N_k\}$ produced by a given star in a single frame. The covariance of any such estimate, based on the observed counts only, will satisfy the inequality

$$\text{Cov}(\hat{\underline{\beta}}) \geq \left[\sum_k \left(\frac{\partial E(N_k | \underline{\beta})}{\partial \underline{\beta}} \right) \left(\frac{\partial E(N_k | \underline{\beta})}{\partial \underline{\beta}} \right)' \frac{1}{E(N_k | \underline{\beta})} \right]_{\underline{\beta} = \underline{\beta}_{\text{true}}}^{-1} \quad (1)$$

derived from the Cramér-Rao bound. ($\underline{A} \geq \underline{B}$ means that $\underline{A} - \underline{B}$ is nonnegative definite.) Here, $E(N_k | \underline{\beta})$ is the expected number of counts in sample k as a function of $\underline{\beta}$. The chosen parametrization is (A.10.11), i.e.

$$E(N_k | \underline{\beta}) = \beta_1 + \beta_2 \left[\cos(H_k + \beta_3) + \beta_4 \cos(2H_k + 2\beta_3) + \beta_5 \sin(2H_k + 2\beta_3) \right] \quad (2)$$

The five signal parameters form two fairly distinct groups: the astrometric signal parameters $\underline{\beta}_a = (\beta_3 \ \beta_5)'$ are intimately related to the phases of the two harmonics and thus to the positional information, while the photometric signal parameters $\underline{\beta}_p = (\beta_1 \ \beta_2 \ \beta_4)'$ are related to the amplitudes of the DC component and the harmonics. It is this latter group which is the object of study here. Actually, one cannot in general separate completely the photometric information from the astrometric: the full 5-vector of signal parameters (with a 5-by-5 covariance matrix) must be considered in the real processing and in any detailed simulations. Under certain assumptions the indicated separation is however not too unrealistic and permits a fairly simple analytical treatment, as will be shown below.

2. BASIC ASSUMPTIONS AND THE SEPARATION OF PARAMETERS

The parametrization (2) relates to the "standard" IDT signal model (A.6.4) (introducing $\psi_k = 2\pi G_k$ and $R = M_2/M_1$ for brevity),

$$E(N_k) = B \Delta t + I_s \Delta t \left[1 + M_1 \cos(\psi_k) + M_2 \cos(2\psi_k - v_2) \right] \quad (3)$$

by means of the identities

$$\left. \begin{aligned} \beta_1 &= (B + I_s) \Delta t \\ \beta_2 &= M_1 I_s \Delta t \\ \beta_3 &= \psi_k - H_k = 2\pi(G_k - \tilde{G}_k) \\ \beta_4 &= R \cos v_2 \\ \beta_5 &= R \sin v_2 \end{aligned} \right\} \quad (4)$$

One effect of the background (B) is to decrease the effective modulation. Eqn (3) can also be written

$$E(N_k) = \beta_1 \left[1 + \mu_1 \cos(\psi_k) + \mu_2 \cos(2\psi_k - v_2) \right] \quad (5)$$

where

$$\mu_i = \frac{I_s}{I_s + B} M_i, \quad i = 1, 2 \quad (6)$$

are the "effective" modulation factors. Note that $\mu_1 = \beta_2/\beta_1$. The partial derivatives in (1) are now

$$\frac{\partial E(N_k | \underline{\beta})}{\partial \underline{\beta}} = \begin{pmatrix} 1 \\ \cos(\psi_k) + R \cos(2\psi_k - v_2) \\ \beta_1 \left[-\mu_1 \sin(\psi_k) - 2\mu_2 \sin(2\psi_k - v_2) \right] \\ \beta_1 \mu_1 \cos(2\psi_k) \\ \beta_1 \mu_1 \sin(2\psi_k) \end{pmatrix} \quad (7)$$

In order to get analytical expressions for the photometric covariances we now make the following assumptions:

- (i) Equality holds in (1); i.e., the covariance is estimated by means of the right-hand side.
- (ii) The modulation phases ψ_k are uniformly distributed in $[0, 2\pi[$.
- (iii) The second harmonic is nearly in phase with the first: $|v_2| \ll 1$.

Numerical experiments have shown (NDAC/LO/004, 012) that (i) is a reasonable approximation when using a Maximum Likelihood estimator on a count sequence with at least $\sim 10^2$ photons ($\sum_k N_k \gtrsim 100$). Assumption (ii) allows the sum in (1) to be written as a multiple of a simple average with respect to $\psi \in [0, 2\pi[$:

$$\sum_k \underline{A}(\psi_k) = \frac{T}{\Delta t} \frac{1}{2\pi} \int_0^{2\pi} \underline{A}(\psi) d\psi = \frac{T}{\Delta t} \langle \underline{A}(\psi) \rangle \quad (8)$$

Here, T is the total integration (observation) time; $T/\Delta t$ is the number of samples in the frame that the star was observed. $\underline{A}$ stands for the (5,5)-matrix defined by (1). The third assumption (iii) permits us to drop v_2 from (5) and (7). The components of the partial derivative (7) become proportional to the simple harmonic functions

$$\left. \begin{aligned} g_1(\psi) &= 1 \\ g_2(\psi) &= \cos \psi + R \cos 2\psi \\ g_3(\psi) &= -\mu_1 \sin \psi - 2\mu_2 \sin 2\psi \\ g_4(\psi) &= \mu_1 \cos 2\psi \\ g_5(\psi) &= \mu_1 \sin 2\psi \end{aligned} \right\} \quad (9)$$

and the bracketed sum in (1) will contain elements proportional to

$$\left\langle \frac{g_i(\psi)g_j(\psi)}{1 + \mu_1 \cos \psi + \mu_2 \cos 2\psi} \right\rangle =: p_{ij} \quad (10)$$

With respect to this "inner product" the g -functions clearly form two mutually orthogonal subsets, viz. the even functions g_1 , g_2 , and g_4 on one

hand, and the odd functions g_3 and g_5 on the other:

$$p_{ij} = 0 \quad \text{for } i \in \{1, 2, 4\} \quad \text{and} \quad j \in \{3, 5\} \quad (11)$$

Under the given assumptions (i) - (iii) there is consequently no correlation between the photometric and the astrometric signal parameters ($\underline{\beta}_p$ and $\underline{\beta}_a$). Their covariances can be completely separated and we find

$$\text{Cov}(\hat{\underline{\beta}}_p) = \frac{\beta_1 \Delta t}{T} \begin{pmatrix} p_{11} & p_{12} & \beta_1 p_{14} \\ p_{12} & p_{22} & \beta_1 p_{24} \\ \beta_1 p_{14} & \beta_1 p_{24} & \beta_1^2 p_{44} \end{pmatrix}^{-1} \quad (12)$$

$$\text{Cov}(\hat{\underline{\beta}}_a) = \frac{\Delta t}{\beta_1 T} \begin{pmatrix} p_{33} & p_{35} \\ p_{35} & p_{55} \end{pmatrix}^{-1} \quad (13)$$

In the following we deal exclusively with the photometric part (12).

3. THE COVARIANCE IN TERMS OF $f_m(\mu_1, \mu_2)$

The p_{ij} in (12) are readily written in terms of the functions

$$f_m(\mu_1, \mu_2) = \left\langle \frac{\cos^m 2\psi}{1 + \mu_1 \cos \psi + \mu_2 \cos 2\psi} \right\rangle \quad (14)$$

for $m = 0, 1, \text{ and } 2$. The result is (dropping the arguments μ_1, μ_2)

$$\left. \begin{aligned} p_{11} &= f_0 & p_{22} &= (f_0 - 1)/\mu_1^2 \\ p_{12} &= (1 - f_0)/\mu_1 & p_{24} &= -f_1 \\ p_{14} &= \mu_1 f_1 & p_{44} &= \mu_1^2 f_2 \end{aligned} \right\} \quad (15)$$

Thus

$$\text{Cov}(\hat{\underline{\beta}}_p) = \frac{\beta_1 \Delta t}{T} \begin{pmatrix} f_0 & (1-f_0)/\mu_1 & \beta_1 \mu_1 f_1 \\ (1-f_0)/\mu_1 & (f_0-1)/\mu_1^2 & -\beta_1 f_1 \\ \beta_1 \mu_1 f_1 & -\beta_1 f_1 & \beta_1^2 \mu_1^2 f_2 \end{pmatrix}^{-1} \quad (16)$$

The determinant of the (3,3)-matrix is

$$\beta_1^2 \begin{vmatrix} f_0 & 1-f_0 & f_1 \\ 1-f_0 & f_0-1 & -f_1 \\ f_1 & -f_1 & f_2 \end{vmatrix} = \beta_1^2 [(f_0-1)f_2 - f_1^2] = \beta_1^2 D \quad (17)$$

so that

$$\text{Cov}(\hat{\underline{\beta}}_p) = \frac{\beta_1 \Delta t}{T} \begin{pmatrix} 1 & \mu_1 & 0 \\ \mu_1 & \mu_1^2(1+f_2/D) & f_1/(\beta_1 D) \\ 0 & f_1/(\beta_1 D) & (f_0-1)/(\beta_1^2 \mu_1^2 D) \end{pmatrix} \quad (18)$$

with

$$D = (f_0 - 1)f_2 - f_1^2 \quad (19)$$

Analytical formulae for $f_m(\mu_1, \mu_2)$ are derived in an Appendix. This also gives tables of f_0, f_1, f_2 , and some useful combinations thereof [e.g. for the elements of (18)].

4. MEAN ERRORS OF THE UNCONSTRAINED ESTIMATES

From $\hat{\underline{\beta}}_p$ we get, by means of (4), direct estimates of the total count rate $I_{\text{tot}} = B + I_s$, the stellar count rate I_s , and the modulation ratio $R = M_2/M_1$:

$$\hat{I}_{\text{tot}} = \Delta t^{-1} \hat{\beta}_1 \quad (20)$$

$$\hat{I}'_s = (\Delta t \tilde{M}_1)^{-1} \hat{\beta}_2 \quad (21)$$

$$\hat{R} = (\hat{\beta}_4^2 + \hat{\beta}_5^2)^{\frac{1}{2}} \approx \hat{\beta}_4 \quad (22)$$

In (22), $\tilde{M}_1$ is the a priori (calibration) value of the modulation factor, and the prime on $\hat{I}'_s$ signifies an estimate based on the first harmonic only.

Using the diagonal elements of (18) we find that the relative mean errors of the estimated count rates are

$$\frac{\sigma(\hat{I}_{\text{tot}})}{I_{\text{tot}}} = \frac{\sigma(\hat{\beta}_1)}{\beta_1} = [\Delta t / (\beta_1 T)]^{\frac{1}{2}} = (I_{\text{tot}} T)^{-1} = N_{\text{tot}}^{-\frac{1}{2}} \quad (23)$$

$$\frac{\sigma(\hat{I}'_s)}{I_s} = \frac{\sigma(\hat{\beta}_2)}{\beta_2} = [1 + f_2/D]^{\frac{1}{2}} N_{\text{tot}}^{-\frac{1}{2}} \quad (24)$$

where $N_{\text{tot}} = (B + I_s)T$ is the total number of counts. The mean error of the estimated modulation ratio is

$$\sigma(\hat{R}) = [(f_0 - 1) / (\mu_1^2 D)]^{\frac{1}{2}} N_{\text{tot}}^{-\frac{1}{2}} \quad (25)$$

Equation (24) is valid only if M_1 is perfectly known. In the practical case of $\sigma(\tilde{M}_1) > 0$ we have instead, assuming uncorrelated $\hat{\beta}_2$ and $\tilde{M}_1$,

$$\left(\frac{\sigma(\hat{I}'_s)}{I_s} \right)^2 = [1 + f_2/D] N_{\text{tot}}^{-1} + \left(\frac{\sigma(\tilde{M}_1)}{M_1} \right)^2 \quad (26)$$

5. MEAN ERROR OF THE FLUX ESTIMATE FROM THE SECOND HARMONIC

In the preceding section we used the calibration value $\tilde{M}_1$ to get an estimate of I_s based entirely on the first harmonic, $\hat{I}'_s = \hat{\beta}_2 / (\tilde{M}_1 \Delta t)$. If we have also a calibration value $\tilde{R}$ for the modulation ratio, we can get a second, partially independent estimate from the second harmonic:

$$\hat{I}_s'' = \hat{\beta}_2 (\hat{\beta}_4^2 + \hat{\beta}_5^2)^{1/2} / (\widetilde{RM}_1 \Delta t) \simeq \hat{\beta}_2 \hat{\beta}_4 / (\widetilde{RM}_1 \Delta t) \quad (27)$$

We shall now derive the mean error of this estimate, being a non-linear combination of several correlated variables.

In general, the variance of any function value

$$\hat{h} = h(\hat{\beta}_p, \widetilde{M}_1, \widetilde{R}) \quad (28)$$

is

$$\sigma^2(\hat{h}) = \begin{pmatrix} \partial h / \partial \beta_1 \\ \partial h / \partial \beta_2 \\ \partial h / \partial \beta_4 \\ \partial h / \partial M_1 \\ \partial h / \partial R \end{pmatrix}' \text{Cov} \begin{pmatrix} \hat{\beta}_p \\ \widetilde{M}_1 \\ \widetilde{R} \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} \partial h / \partial \beta_1 \\ \partial h / \partial \beta_2 \\ \partial h / \partial \beta_4 \\ \partial h / \partial M_1 \\ \partial h / \partial R \end{pmatrix} \quad (29)$$

in which the partial derivatives are to be evaluated at the true values of β_p , M_1 , and R . We may assume that $\widetilde{M}_1$ and $\widetilde{R}$ are statistically independent of each other (cf Section 8) and of $\hat{\beta}_p$, so that

$$\begin{aligned} \sigma^2(\hat{h}) &= \begin{pmatrix} \frac{\partial h}{\partial \beta_1} & \frac{\partial h}{\partial \beta_2} & \frac{\partial h}{\partial \beta_4} \end{pmatrix} \text{Cov}(\hat{\beta}_p) \begin{pmatrix} \frac{\partial h}{\partial \beta_1} \\ \frac{\partial h}{\partial \beta_2} \\ \frac{\partial h}{\partial \beta_4} \end{pmatrix} + \\ &+ \left(\frac{\partial h}{\partial M_1} \right)^2 \sigma^2(\widetilde{M}_1) + \left(\frac{\partial h}{\partial R} \right)^2 \sigma^2(\widetilde{R}) \end{aligned} \quad (30)$$

Applying (28) - (30) on the particular problem $\hat{h} = \hat{I}_s''$ according to (27),

$$\frac{\partial h}{\partial \beta_1} = 0, \quad \frac{\partial h}{\partial \beta_2} = 1/(M_1 \Delta t), \quad \frac{\partial h}{\partial \beta_4} = \mu_1 \beta_1 / (M_2 \Delta t),$$

$$\frac{\partial h}{\partial M_1} = -\mu_1 \beta_1 / (M_1^2 \Delta t), \quad \frac{\partial h}{\partial R} = -\mu_1 \beta_1 / (M_2 \Delta t) \quad (31)$$

and hence

$$\left(\frac{\sigma(\hat{I}_s'')}{I_s}\right)^2 = \left[1 + \frac{f_2}{D} + \frac{2f_1}{D\mu_2} + \frac{f_0 - 1}{D\mu_2^2}\right] N_{\text{tot}}^{-1} + \left(\frac{\sigma(\tilde{M}_1)}{M_1}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{\sigma(\tilde{R})}{R}\right)^2 \quad (32)$$

In the absence of calibration errors [$\sigma(\tilde{M}_1) = \sigma(\tilde{R}) = 0$] or when photon-statistical errors dominate, we have for $\mu_1 = 0.68$, $\mu_2 = 0.24$

$$\frac{\sigma(\hat{I}_s'')}{\sigma(\hat{I}_s')} \approx 2.5 \quad (33)$$

which would seem to indicate that the first harmonic carries about six times the (photometric) weight of the second harmonic. We shall see, however, that the interpretation is not as simple as that, due to the correlation between the two estimates.

If the full covariance of $\hat{I}_s'$ and $\hat{I}_s''$ is wanted, we may write

$$\underline{\hat{h}} = \begin{pmatrix} \hat{I}_s' \\ \hat{I}_s'' \end{pmatrix} \quad (34)$$

and extend (29) with a second column of partial derivatives. We find thus

$$I_s^{-2} \text{Cov} \begin{pmatrix} \hat{I}_s' \\ \hat{I}_s'' \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} 1 + f_2/D & 1 + f_2/D + f_1/(D\mu_2) \\ \dots & 1 + f_2/D + 2f_1/(D\mu_2) + (f_0 - 1)/(D\mu_2^2) \end{pmatrix} N_{\text{tot}}^{-1} + \begin{pmatrix} \sigma^2(\tilde{M}_1)/M_1^2 & \sigma^2(\tilde{M}_1)/M_1^2 \\ \dots & \sigma^2(\tilde{M}_1)/M_1^2 + \sigma^2(\tilde{R})/R^2 \end{pmatrix} \quad (35)$$

(omitting the redundant elements of the symmetric matrices). For $\mu_1 = 0.68$, $\mu_2 = 0.24$ the correlation coefficient ranges from ≈ 0.3 when photon errors dominate, to ≈ 0.7 when calibration errors dominate [assuming $\sigma(\tilde{M}_1)/M_1 \approx \sigma(\tilde{R})/R$].

6. MEAN ERROR OF THE CONSTRAINED ESTIMATE

A constrained estimate of the stellar count rate, $\hat{I}_s^c$, is obtained by imposing $R = \tilde{R}$ on the solution. The covariance of the resulting $\hat{\beta}_1^c, \hat{\beta}_2^c$ is simply obtained by deleting the third row and column in (16), yielding

$$\text{Cov} \begin{pmatrix} \hat{\beta}_1^c \\ \hat{\beta}_2^c \end{pmatrix} = \beta_1^2 N_{\text{tot}}^{-1} \begin{pmatrix} 1 & \mu_1 \\ \mu_1 & f_0 \mu_1^2 / (f_0 - 1) \end{pmatrix} \quad (36)$$

Clearly only β_2 is affected by the constraint. The new relative mean error is

$$\frac{\sigma(\hat{I}_s^c)}{I_s} = [f_0 / (f_0 - 1)]^{\frac{1}{2}} N_{\text{tot}}^{-\frac{1}{2}} \quad (37)$$

to be compared with (24) for the unconstrained $\hat{I}_s'$. The improvement factor is

$$\frac{\sigma(\hat{I}_s^c)}{\sigma(\hat{I}_s')} = [1 + f_1^2 / (Df_0)]^{-\frac{1}{2}} \quad (38)$$

or ≈ 0.995 for $\mu_1 = 0.68, \mu_2 = 0.24$.

This remarkably small improvement is clearly due to the relative size of f_1 , which actually disappears for certain, quite realistic, combinations of μ_1, μ_2 (Table 2). Thus there exist cases when the second harmonic contains absolutely no photometric information in addition to that of the first harmonic, even though $\mu_2 > 0$! The typical situation is in fact not far from this condition.

The constrained estimate can also be regarded as an optimally weighted mean of the two estimates $\hat{I}_s'$ and $\hat{I}_s''$ from the first and second harmonics:

$$\hat{I}_s^W = (1 - w)\hat{I}_s' + w\hat{I}_s'' \quad (39)$$

where w is chosen to minimize $\sigma(\hat{I}_s^W)$. Then $\hat{I}_s^W = \hat{I}_s^c$. We have

$$\begin{aligned}
\sigma^2(\hat{I}_s^w) &= (1-w \quad w) \text{Cov} \begin{pmatrix} \hat{I}_s' \\ \hat{I}_s'' \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} 1-w \\ w \end{pmatrix} = \\
&= \frac{I_s^2}{N_{\text{tot}}} \left[(1-w)^2 \left(1 + \frac{f_2}{D}\right) + 2w(1-w) \left(1 + \frac{f_2}{D} + \frac{f_1}{D\mu_2}\right) + \right. \\
&\quad \left. + w^2 \left(1 + \frac{f_2}{D} + \frac{2f_1}{D\mu_2} + \frac{f_0^{-1}}{D\mu_2^2}\right) \right] \quad (40)
\end{aligned}$$

after insertion of the photon-statistical part of (35). This is minimized by

$$w = -\mu_2 f_1 / (f_0 - 1) \quad (41)$$

yielding

$$\sigma^2(\hat{I}_s^w)_{\text{min}} = \frac{I_s^2}{N_{\text{tot}}} \frac{f_0}{f_0 - 1} \quad (42)$$

i.e., identical to $\sigma^2(\hat{I}_s^c)$ in (37). We see that the relative weight of $\hat{I}_s''$ becomes $w = 0$ whenever $f_1 = 0$. For $\mu_1 = 0.68$, $\mu_2 = 0.24$ we have $w \approx 0.04$.

7. MEAN ERROR OF THE PARTIALLY CONSTRAINED ESTIMATE

The constrained estimation in Section 6 means that infinite weight is given to the calibration value $\tilde{R}$, while it receives no weight in the unconstrained case of Section 4. In practice, the weight is of course finite and equal to $\sigma(\tilde{R})^{-2}$. The covariance of the partially constrained (pc) vector is obtained by adding the corresponding information (weight) matrices:

$$\text{Cov}(\hat{\beta}_p^{\text{pc}})^{-1} = \text{Cov}(\hat{\beta}_p)^{-1} + \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & \sigma(\tilde{R})^2 \end{pmatrix}^{-1} \quad (43)$$

In (16) the third diagonal element of the information matrix is $N_{\text{tot}} \mu_1^2 f_2$, to which is added $\sigma(\tilde{R})^{-2}$. Since f_2 does not appear anywhere else in (16),

this operation is equivalent to replacing f_2 by

$$f_2' = f_2 + [N_{\text{tot}} \mu_1^2 \sigma^2(\tilde{R})]^{-1} \quad (44)$$

With this substitution (which also modifies $D!$), Eqns (18) - (26) hold also for the partially constrained case. In particular, from (24),

$$\frac{\sigma(\hat{I}_s^{\text{PC}})}{I_s} = \left[\frac{f_0 f_2' - f_1^2}{(f_0 - 1) f_2' - f_1^2} \right]^{\frac{1}{2}} N_{\text{tot}}^{-\frac{1}{2}} \quad (45)$$

which in the limit $\sigma(\tilde{R}) \rightarrow 0$ ($f_2' \rightarrow \infty$) becomes (37).

8. CORRELATION OF THE CALIBRATION VALUES $\tilde{M}_1$ AND $\tilde{R}$

$\tilde{M}_1$ and $\tilde{R}$ may be calibrated as functions of field position and colour by means of relatively bright stars, for which the background has little influence ($B \ll I_s$). We shall now consider the joint determination of M_1 and R from such an observation, for which an a priori value $\tilde{B}$ for the background may be available (from quasi-simultaneous observations of faint stars). The estimates, which eventually go into the calibration values, are

$$\hat{M}_1 = \hat{\beta}_2 / (\hat{\beta}_1 - \tilde{B} \Delta t) \simeq \hat{\beta}_2 / \hat{\beta}_1 \quad (46)$$

$$\hat{R} = (\hat{\beta}_4^2 + \hat{\beta}_5^2)^{\frac{1}{2}} \simeq \hat{\beta}_4 \quad (47)$$

(the indicated approximations are only for the present error analysis). We neglect the error contribution from $\tilde{B}$ and put $B = 0$ ($\mu_1 = M_1$) in the equations below. Using the method outlined in Section 5 with $\hat{h} = (\hat{M}_1, \hat{R})'$ and partial derivatives

$$\begin{aligned} \partial M_1 / \partial \beta_1 &= -M_1 / \beta_1, & \partial R / \partial \beta_1 &= 0 \\ \partial M_1 / \partial \beta_2 &= 1 / \beta_1, & \partial R / \partial \beta_2 &= 0 \\ \partial M_1 / \partial \beta_4 &= 0, & \partial R / \partial \beta_4 &= 1 \end{aligned} \quad (48)$$

we find

$$\text{Cov} \begin{pmatrix} \hat{M}_1 \\ R \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} M_1^2 f_2/D & f_1/D \\ f_1/D & (f_0-1)/(DM_1^2) \end{pmatrix} N_{\text{tot}}^{-1} \quad (49)$$

Thus

$$\frac{\sigma(\hat{M}_1)}{M_1} = (f_2/D)^{\frac{1}{2}} N_{\text{tot}}^{-\frac{1}{2}} \quad (50)$$

while the result for $\sigma(\hat{R})$ is of course identical to (25).

Most surprising is perhaps that the correlation between $\hat{M}_1$ and $\hat{R}$,

$$\rho(\hat{M}_1, \hat{R}) = f_1 [(f_0-1)f_2]^{-\frac{1}{2}} \quad (51)$$

is typically rather small, $\rho \approx -0.10$ for $\mu_1 = 0.68$, $\mu_2 = 0.24$. It turns out that the correlation between $\hat{M}_1$ and $\hat{M}_2 = \hat{R}\hat{M}_1$ is more considerable, or about +0.25 in typical cases. That $\hat{M}_1$ and $\hat{R}$ are nearly statistically independent makes them particularly suitable as calibration parameters.

9. MEAN ERROR OF THE BACKGROUND ESTIMATE $\hat{B}$

For the background estimate

$$\hat{B} = \hat{I}_{\text{tot}} - \hat{I}'_s = \Delta t^{-1} \hat{\beta}_1 - (\Delta t \tilde{M}_1)^{-1} \hat{\beta}_2 \quad (52)$$

we find the variance

$$\sigma^2(\hat{B}) = [(B + 2I_s)^2 + I_s^2 f_2/D] N_{\text{tot}}^{-1} + I_s^2 \left(\frac{\sigma(\tilde{M}_1)}{M_1} \right)^2 \quad (53)$$

Since $f_2/D \sim 10$ for faint stars, we can expect a sensible determination of B from a single frame [$\sigma(\hat{B}) \lesssim B$] only when $I_s \lesssim 0.1 T B^2$, or about 200 Hz ($m_B \gtrsim 11.5$) for $B \approx 50$ Hz.

10. CONCLUSIONS AND DISCUSSION

Under the assumptions listed on page 3 we have made a fairly complete analytical study of the photometric errors. Probably all three assumptions work in the direction of making the estimates slightly optimistic, especially for the faint stars, so the results should be used with caution. However, the following conclusions seem to be well founded:

(a) The second harmonic contributes practically no photometric information in addition to that of the first harmonic and the DC component. It is consequently suggested that it is ignored in the photometric processing.

(b) The mean error of the stellar count rate (I_s) as derived from $\hat{\beta}_2$ is 2.1-3 times that of the total count rate ($I_{\text{tot}} = B + I_s$) derived from $\hat{\beta}_1$.

(c) The background count rate (B) can only be derived from observations of the faintest stars, $m_B \gtrsim 11.5$ ($I_s \lesssim 200$ Hz) for typical B.

Point (b) is a real dilemma, in that we have one unbiased estimate $\hat{I}'_s$ of the stellar count rate with a large mean error, and a second, biased "estimate" $\hat{I}_{\text{tot}}$ with a much smaller mean error. If $B \approx 50$ Hz, the bias exceeds 0.01 mag for $I_s \lesssim 5000$ Hz or $m_B \gtrsim 8$.

It appears that one of the following solutions must be chosen:

(I) Only the estimate $\hat{I}'_s$ is used, in spite of the larger random errors. In this case there is no point in calibrating M_1 , since the product $M_1 I_s$ is the natural brightness measure. Any variations of M_1 due to focus, for instance, will go into the determination of the (field dependent) magnitude zero point. Since M_1 depends on the colour, $M_1 I_s$ has a slightly different (bluer) effective wavelength than I_s .

(II) Only the biased estimate $\hat{I}_s$ is used, possibly with a nominal correction for the background. Again, M_1 need not be calibrated. One would then hope that the photometric calibration by means of standard stars will be able to cope with the bias, e.g. by means of special, time dependent, non-linearity terms. (In effect, B is determined a posteriori as function of time by means of standard stars. It is then very important to have a good number of faint standards.)

(III) The background is determined as function of time, $\tilde{B}(t)$ (neglecting field variations other than "fixed-pattern" sensitivity variations), by means of (52) applied on faint stars. The stellar count rate is then estimated as $\hat{I}_s = \hat{I}_{\text{tot}} - \tilde{B}(t)$. This requires that M_1 is calibrated as function of field position and colour. The faint stars used to determine $\tilde{B}(t)$ need not be standard stars [in contrast to (II)], but knowing their colours will of course improve the determination, since the colour uncertainty goes into $\sigma(\tilde{M}_1)$.

Of the three methods, (I) is the simplest and probably least prone to give systematic (linearity) errors; it is however also the least precise. (II) is not to be recommended in view of the obvious risk of biases or even indeterminacy, viz. in the absence of faint standard stars. (III) seems to offer the best compromise between precision and unbiasedness, but is more complicated.

APPENDIX: EVALUATION OF f_0 , f_1 , and f_2

The functions $f_m(\mu_1, \mu_2)$ defined in (14) can be expressed by means of the simpler functions

$$e_m(x) = \left\langle \frac{\cos^m 2\psi}{x + \cos \psi} \right\rangle \quad (\text{A.1})$$

by using that

$$e_m(x) - e_m(y) = \left\langle \frac{2(y-x)\cos^m 2\psi}{(1+2xy) + 2(x+y)\cos \psi + \cos 2\psi} \right\rangle \quad (\text{A.2})$$

Thus,

$$f_m(\mu_1, \mu_2) = \frac{1+2xy}{2(y-x)} \left[e_m(x) - e_m(y) \right] \quad (\text{A.3})$$

provided that x, y satisfy

$$\frac{2(x+y)}{1+2xy} = \mu_1, \quad \frac{1}{1+2xy} = \mu_2 \quad (\text{A.4})$$

We find

$$x = \left[\mu_1 - [\mu_1^2 - 8\mu_2(1-\mu_2)]^{\frac{1}{2}} \right] / (4\mu_2),$$

$$y = \left[\mu_1 + [\mu_1^2 - 8\mu_2(1-\mu_2)]^{\frac{1}{2}} \right] / (4\mu_2) \quad (\text{A.5})$$

(and a second solution by exchanging x and y). Note that in most cases of practical interest, $\mu_1^2 < 8\mu_2(1-\mu_2)$, so that x and y are usually complex conjugates. This can be used to simplify some results, but we shall not make use of it here.

Consider now the integral

$$e_m(x) = \frac{1}{2\pi} \int_0^{2\pi} \frac{\cos^m 2\psi}{x + \cos \psi} d\psi \quad (\text{A.6})$$

for arbitrary (complex) argument x . Substituting $z = \exp(j\psi)$ we obtain a contour integral along the unit circle in the complex plane:

$$\begin{aligned} e_m(x) &= \frac{1}{2\pi} \oint_{|z|=1} \frac{[\frac{1}{2}(z^2 + z^{-2})]^m dz}{x + \frac{1}{2}(z + z^{-1})} \frac{1}{jz} \\ &= \frac{2^{-m}}{j\pi} \oint_{|z|=1} \frac{(1 + z^4)^m dz}{z^{2m}(1 + 2xz + z^2)} \end{aligned} \quad (\text{A.7})$$

which can be solved by means of the residue theorem. The integrand has a pole of order $2m$ at $z_0 = 0$ and simple poles at

$$z_{1,2} = -x \pm (x^2 - 1)^{\frac{1}{2}} \quad (\text{A.8})$$

Since $z_1 z_2 = 1$, only one of them is inside the unit circle. As it turns out, the positive sign in (A.8) gives the desired pole:

$$|z_1| < 1 \quad \text{for} \quad z_1 = -x + (x^2 - 1)^{\frac{1}{2}} \quad (\text{A.9})$$

The residue at $z = z_1$ is

$$R_1(m) = \frac{(1 + z_1^4)^m}{z_1^{2m}(z_1 - z_2)} = \frac{(z_1^2 + z_1^{-2})^m}{z_1 - z_1^{-1}} = \frac{(2x^2 - 1)^m}{(x^2 - 1)^{\frac{1}{2}}} \quad (\text{A.10})$$

while at $z = z_0 = 0$,

$$R_0(m) = \lim_{z \rightarrow z_0} \frac{1}{(2m-1)!} \frac{d^{2m-1}}{dz^{2m-1}} \left[\frac{(1 + z^4)^m}{1 + 2xz + z^2} \right] \quad (\text{A.11})$$

If the expression in brackets is expanded in a power series by direct division,

$$\frac{1 + mz^4 + \frac{1}{2}m(m-1)z^8 + \dots}{1 + 2xz + z^2} = 1 - 2xz + (4x^2 - 1)z^2 - 4x(2x^2 - 1)z^3 + \dots \quad (\text{A.12})$$

we see that $R_0(m)$ is simply the coefficient of z^{2m-1} in the series. Thus

$$\left. \begin{aligned} R_0(0) &= 0 && \text{(no pole at } z = 0) \\ R_0(1) &= -2x \\ R_0(2) &= -4x(2x^2 - 1) \end{aligned} \right\} \quad (\text{A.13})$$

From the residue theorem we now have

$$\oint_{|z|=1} \frac{(1+z^4)^m dz}{z^{2m}(1+2xz+z^2)} = 2\pi j \left[R_0(m) + R_1(m) \right] \quad (\text{A.14})$$

and by (A.7),

$$e_m(x) = 2^{1-m} \left[R_0(m) + R_1(m) \right] \quad (\text{A.15})$$

Inserting (A.13) and (A.10) yields

$$\begin{aligned} e_0(x) &= (x^2 - 1)^{-\frac{1}{2}}, \\ e_1(x) &= [x - (x^2 - 1)^{\frac{1}{2}}]^2 e_0(x), \\ e_2(x) &= (2x^2 - 1) e_1(x) \end{aligned} \quad (\text{A.16})$$

and the final expressions for f_m become

$$f_m(\mu_1, \mu_2) = [\mu_1^2 - 8\mu_2(1 - \mu_2)]^{-\frac{1}{2}} [e_m(x) - e_m(y)] \quad (\text{A.17})$$

A FORTRAN subroutine FM has been written which computes f_0 , f_1 , and f_2 as functions of μ_1 (= A) and μ_2 (= B). It has been tested against direct numerical averaging of (14) and was used to produce the tables at the end of this note.

```

0001      SUBROUTINE      FM (A, B,      FD, F1, F2)
0002      C
0003      C  EVALUATION OF
0004      C
0005      C                                COS(2*V)**M
0006      C  FM = < ----- >
0007      C                    1 + A*COS(V) + B*COS(2*V)
0008      C
0009      C  FOR M = 0, 1, AND 2 (FD, F1, F2).
0010      C
0011      C  METHOD:
0012      C  COMPLEX ANALYTICAL FORMULA (LINDEGREN 1983-08-22, APPENDIX)
0013      C
0014      C      COMPLEX  ONE, TWO, C, CA, CB, X, Y, SX, SY, EX, EY
0015      C      DATA  ONE, TWO / (1., D.), (2., D.) /
0016      C      C = CSQRT(  CMPLX(A**2-B.*B*(1.-B), D.)  )
0017      C      CA = CMPLX(A, D.)
0018      C      CB = CMPLX(.25/B, D.)
0019      C      X = (CA - C)*CB
0020      C      Y = (CA + C)*CB
0021      C      SX = CSQRT(X**2 - ONE)
0022      C      SY = CSQRT(Y**2 - ONE)
0023      C      EX = ONE/(C*SX)
0024      C      EY = ONE/(C*SY)
0025      C      FD = REAL(EX - EY)
0026      C      EX = (X - SX)**2*EX
0027      C      EY = (Y - SY)**2*EY
0028      C      F1 = REAL(EX - EY)
0029      C      EX = (TWO*X**2 - ONE)*EX
0030      C      EY = (TWO*Y**2 - ONE)*EY
0031      C      F2 = REAL(EX - EY)
0032      C      RETURN
0033      C      END

```

Avoiding complex arithmetics [case $\mu_1^2 < 8\mu_2(1-\mu_2)$]

As previously mentioned, x and y are usually complex in practical cases. The FORTRAN subroutine FM handles both the real and complex cases, but if we restrict ourselves now to the complex case, $\mu_1^2 < 8\mu_2(1-\mu_2)$, we can find more explicit formulae avoiding the use of complex arithmetic. Thus

$$y = x^*$$

We see immediately from (A.1) that $e_m(x^*) = e_m(x)^*$, so that (A.17) becomes

$$f_m = [8\mu_2(1 - \mu_2) - \mu_1^2]^{-\frac{1}{2}} 2\text{Im}[e_m(x)] \quad (\text{A.19})$$

After some manipulation we find that f_m can be calculated by the following steps, involving only real numbers:

$$r = 4\mu_2[(1 + \mu_2)^2 - \mu_1^2]^{\frac{1}{2}}$$

$$s = 1 - \mu_1^2/(4\mu_2)$$

$$t = 4\mu_2(1 + \mu_2) - \mu_1^2$$

$$f_0 = \frac{2}{r} \left[\frac{\mu_2(r + t)}{1 - 2\mu_2 + s} \right]^{\frac{1}{2}}$$

$$f_1 = [1 - sf_0 - \mu_1(r - t)^{\frac{1}{2}}/r]/\mu_2$$

$$f_2 = [(2 - \mu_2^{-1})(f_0 - 1) + 2(1 - sf_0 - sf_1)]/\mu_2 \quad (\text{A.20})$$

TABLES

NO.	QUANTITY	EQN	RELEVANT FOR
1.	$f_0 = \left\langle \frac{1}{1 + \mu_1 \cos \psi + \mu_2 \cos 2\psi} \right\rangle$	--	--
2.	$f_1 = \left\langle \frac{\cos 2\psi}{1 + \mu_1 \cos \psi + \mu_2 \cos 2\psi} \right\rangle$	--	--
3.	$f_2 = \left\langle \frac{\cos^2 2\psi}{1 + \mu_2 \cos \psi + \mu_2 \cos 2\psi} \right\rangle$	--	--
4.	$D = (f_0 - 1)f_2 - f_1^2$	--	--
5.	$[1 + f_2/D]^{\frac{1}{2}}$	(24), (26)	mean error of $\hat{I}'_s$
6.	$[f_0/(f_0 - 1)]^{\frac{1}{2}}$	(37)	mean error of $\hat{I}^c_s$
7.	$[1 + f_1^2/(Df_0)]^{-\frac{1}{2}}$	(38)	ratio $\frac{\text{constrained m.e.}}{\text{unconstrained m.e.}}$
8.	$(f_2/D)^{\frac{1}{2}}$	(50)	relative m.e. of $\hat{M}_1$
9.	$[(f_0 - 1)/(D\mu_1^2)]^{\frac{1}{2}}$	(25)	m.e. of $\hat{R}$

TABLE OF F0(M1, M2)

M1\M2=	.060	.080	.100	.120	.140	.160	.180	.200	.220	.240	.260	.280	.300	.320	.340	.360
.300	1.04590	1.04614	1.04689	1.04815	1.04992	1.05220	1.05502	1.05837	1.06227	1.06674	1.07179	1.07745	1.08374	1.09069	1.09834	1.10673
.310	1.04910	1.04925	1.04994	1.05109	1.05279	1.05502	1.05777	1.06107	1.06493	1.06935	1.07437	1.07999	1.08626	1.09319	1.10082	1.10920
.320	1.05244	1.05249	1.05306	1.05416	1.05578	1.05794	1.06064	1.06388	1.06760	1.07179	1.07705	1.08264	1.08888	1.09579	1.10341	1.11177
.330	1.05591	1.05586	1.05634	1.05735	1.05890	1.06099	1.06362	1.06680	1.07056	1.07490	1.07983	1.08539	1.09160	1.09849	1.10609	1.11444
.340	1.05953	1.05936	1.05975	1.06067	1.06214	1.06415	1.06671	1.06984	1.07354	1.07783	1.08273	1.08825	1.09443	1.10129	1.10887	1.11720
.350	1.06329	1.06301	1.06339	1.06412	1.06550	1.06743	1.06993	1.07299	1.07664	1.08087	1.08573	1.09121	1.09736	1.10419	1.11175	1.12007
.360	1.06720	1.06680	1.06697	1.06770	1.06899	1.07085	1.07327	1.07626	1.07985	1.08403	1.08884	1.09428	1.10040	1.10720	1.11474	1.12304
.370	1.07127	1.07075	1.07080	1.07142	1.07262	1.07438	1.07673	1.07965	1.08318	1.08731	1.09206	1.09747	1.10354	1.11032	1.11783	1.12612
.380	1.07549	1.07484	1.07477	1.07529	1.07638	1.07806	1.08032	1.08317	1.08653	1.09070	1.09540	1.10076	1.10680	1.11355	1.12104	1.12931
.390	1.07989	1.07909	1.07889	1.07929	1.08028	1.08186	1.08404	1.08681	1.09020	1.09421	1.09886	1.10417	1.10957	1.11589	1.12435	1.13261
.400	1.08444	1.08350	1.08317	1.08345	1.08433	1.08581	1.08789	1.09059	1.09390	1.09785	1.10244	1.10771	1.11366	1.12034	1.12778	1.13601
.410	1.08918	1.08808	1.08761	1.08776	1.08852	1.08990	1.09189	1.09449	1.09773	1.10161	1.10615	1.11136	1.11727	1.12392	1.13132	1.13954
.420	1.09409	1.09283	1.09221	1.09223	1.09287	1.09413	1.09602	1.09854	1.10170	1.10550	1.10998	1.11514	1.12100	1.12761	1.13499	1.14318
.430	1.09919	1.09776	1.09698	1.09686	1.09737	1.09852	1.10030	1.10273	1.10580	1.10953	1.11394	1.11904	1.12486	1.13142	1.13877	1.14694
.440	1.10449	1.10287	1.10193	1.10166	1.10203	1.10306	1.10473	1.10706	1.11004	1.11370	1.11803	1.12307	1.12884	1.13537	1.14268	1.15082
.450	1.10998	1.10818	1.10706	1.10663	1.10716	1.10776	1.10932	1.11154	1.11443	1.11800	1.12226	1.12724	1.13296	1.13944	1.14671	1.15483
.460	1.11568	1.11367	1.11238	1.11178	1.11262	1.11366	1.11496	1.11617	1.11896	1.12245	1.12664	1.13171	1.13764	1.14364	1.15088	1.15896
.470	1.12160	1.11938	1.11789	1.11711	1.11784	1.11876	1.11987	1.12096	1.12365	1.12705	1.13115	1.13600	1.14160	1.14798	1.15518	1.16323
.480	1.12774	1.12539	1.12360	1.12264	1.12240	1.12287	1.12404	1.12592	1.12850	1.13180	1.13582	1.14059	1.14613	1.15245	1.15961	1.16763
.490	1.13411	1.13143	1.12952	1.12837	1.12795	1.12826	1.12929	1.13104	1.13351	1.13670	1.14064	1.14533	1.15080	1.15707	1.16419	1.17218
.500	1.14073	1.13779	1.13566	1.13430	1.13370	1.13384	1.13472	1.13634	1.13868	1.14177	1.14562	1.15023	1.15563	1.16184	1.16891	1.17686
.510	1.14759	1.14439	1.14201	1.14044	1.13965	1.13959	1.14034	1.14181	1.14401	1.14701	1.15075	1.15528	1.16060	1.16676	1.17377	1.18169
.520	1.15472	1.15124	1.14861	1.14681	1.14581	1.14559	1.14611	1.14747	1.14956	1.15242	1.15606	1.16049	1.16574	1.17183	1.17879	1.18667
.530	1.16212	1.15834	1.15545	1.15340	1.15218	1.15177	1.15215	1.15332	1.15527	1.15801	1.16154	1.16588	1.17104	1.17706	1.18397	1.19180
.540	1.16981	1.16571	1.16254	1.16024	1.15879	1.15817	1.15837	1.15937	1.16117	1.16378	1.16719	1.17143	1.17651	1.18246	1.18931	1.19709
.550	1.17780	1.17337	1.16989	1.16732	1.16563	1.16480	1.16480	1.16563	1.16727	1.16974	1.17303	1.17717	1.18216	1.18803	1.19481	1.20255
.560	1.18610	1.18131	1.17752	1.17466	1.17272	1.17165	1.17145	1.17209	1.17358	1.17590	1.17906	1.18309	1.18798	1.19377	1.20049	1.20817
.570	1.19473	1.18957	1.18543	1.18228	1.18006	1.17875	1.17833	1.17878	1.18009	1.18226	1.18529	1.18919	1.19399	1.19969	1.20634	1.21397
.580	1.20370	1.19814	1.19365	1.19017	1.18767	1.18610	1.18545	1.18570	1.18682	1.18883	1.19172	1.19550	1.20018	1.20580	1.21237	1.21994
.590	1.21304	1.20705	1.20218	1.19836	1.19555	1.19372	1.19282	1.19285	1.19378	1.19562	1.19836	1.20201	1.20658	1.21210	1.21860	1.22610
.600	1.22276	1.21631	1.21104	1.20686	1.20373	1.20161	1.20045	1.20025	1.20098	1.20264	1.20522	1.20873	1.21318	1.21860	1.22501	1.23245
.610	1.23288	1.22595	1.22024	1.21568	1.21221	1.20978	1.20835	1.20791	1.20843	1.20989	1.21230	1.21567	1.21999	1.22530	1.23163	1.23900
.620	1.24342	1.23598	1.22981	1.22484	1.22100	1.21825	1.21650	1.21584	1.21612	1.21739	1.21962	1.22283	1.22702	1.23222	1.23845	1.24575
.630	1.25441	1.24641	1.23976	1.23435	1.23013	1.22703	1.22502	1.22404	1.22409	1.22514	1.22718	1.23023	1.23428	1.23936	1.24549	1.25271
.640	1.26588	1.25729	1.25011	1.24424	1.23961	1.23615	1.23380	1.23254	1.23233	1.23315	1.23500	1.23787	1.24178	1.24673	1.25275	1.25988
.650	1.27784	1.26862	1.26088	1.25452	1.24945	1.24560	1.24291	1.24134	1.24086	1.24144	1.24308	1.24577	1.24951	1.25433	1.26024	1.26728
.660	1.29034	1.28044	1.27210	1.26521	1.25968	1.25541	1.25236	1.25046	1.24969	1.25002	1.25144	1.25393	1.25750	1.26218	1.26797	1.27492
.670	1.30340	1.29277	1.28379	1.27634	1.27031	1.26560	1.26215	1.25991	1.25884	1.25890	1.26008	1.26236	1.26576	1.27028	1.27595	1.28279
.680	1.31706	1.30565	1.29598	1.28793	1.28136	1.27618	1.27232	1.26971	1.26832	1.26809	1.26901	1.27108	1.27429	1.27865	1.28418	1.29092
.690	1.33137	1.31911	1.30870	1.30000	1.29286	1.28719	1.28288	1.27988	1.27814	1.27761	1.27826	1.28010	1.28311	1.28730	1.29269	1.29930
.700	1.34636	1.33314	1.32199	1.31259	1.30484	1.29863	1.29385	1.29043	1.28832	1.28746	1.28784	1.28943	1.29222	1.29623	1.30147	1.30796
.710	1.36208	1.34792	1.33587	1.32572	1.31732	1.31053	1.30525	1.30139	1.29888	1.29768	1.29776	1.29908	1.30165	1.30546	1.31054	1.31690
.720	1.37859	1.36336	1.35038	1.33944	1.33033	1.32292	1.31710	1.31276	1.30984	1.30827	1.30803	1.30907	1.31140	1.31501	1.31991	1.32613
.730	1.39595	1.37956	1.36558	1.35376	1.34390	1.33584	1.32943	1.32459	1.32122	1.31926	1.31867	1.31942	1.32149	1.32488	1.32959	1.33566
.740	1.41421	1.39656	1.38150	1.36875	1.35807	1.34930	1.34227	1.33688	1.33303	1.33066	1.32971	1.33014	1.33193	1.33508	1.33960	1.34551
.750	1.43346	1.41444	1.39870	1.38443	1.37288	1.36334	1.35564	1.34967	1.34531	1.34249	1.34115	1.34124	1.34275	1.34565	1.34996	1.35569
.760	1.45378	1.43325	1.41573	1.40086	1.38836	1.37800	1.36959	1.36299	1.35808	1.35479	1.35303	1.35276	1.35376	1.35659	1.36077	1.36622
.770	1.47525	1.45308	1.43416	1.41810	1.40457	1.39331	1.38416	1.37686	1.37137	1.36756	1.36536	1.36470	1.36556	1.36791	1.37176	1.37711
.780	1.49797	1.47399	1.45355	1.43619	1.42155	1.40933	1.39932	1.39132	1.38520	1.38084	1.37816	1.37709	1.37760	1.37965	1.38324	1.38838
.790	1.52207	1.49610	1.47399	1.45521	1.43935	1.42610	1.41518	1.40641	1.39961	1.39467	1.39147	1.38996	1.39008	1.39181	1.39512	1.40004

TABLE 2

TABLE OF F1(M1, M2)

M1\M2=	.060	.080	.100	.120	.140	.160	.180	.200	.220	.240	.260	.280	.300	.320	.340	.360
.300	-.00960	-.02097	-.03234	-.04374	-.05520	-.06675	-.07840	-.09020	-.10217	-.11434	-.12674	-.13940	-.15237	-.16567	-.17936	-.19347
.310	-.00808	-.01954	-.03100	-.04249	-.05403	-.06565	-.07739	-.08926	-.10129	-.11353	-.12599	-.13871	-.15174	-.16510	-.17885	-.19302
.320	-.00649	-.01805	-.02961	-.04118	-.05281	-.06452	-.07632	-.08824	-.10037	-.11268	-.12520	-.13799	-.15108	-.16451	-.17832	-.19255
.330	-.00483	-.01650	-.02815	-.03982	-.05154	-.06333	-.07522	-.08724	-.09942	-.11179	-.12439	-.13724	-.15040	-.16389	-.17776	-.19206
.340	-.00309	-.01487	-.02663	-.03840	-.05021	-.06209	-.07406	-.08616	-.09842	-.11087	-.12354	-.13646	-.14969	-.16324	-.17718	-.19155
.350	-.00128	-.01317	-.02504	-.03692	-.04882	-.06079	-.07286	-.08504	-.09738	-.10990	-.12265	-.13565	-.14894	-.16257	-.17658	-.19101
.360	.00061	-.01141	-.02339	-.03537	-.04738	-.05945	-.07160	-.08387	-.09630	-.10890	-.12173	-.13480	-.14817	-.16187	-.17595	-.19046
.370	.00259	-.00956	-.02166	-.03376	-.04587	-.05804	-.07029	-.08266	-.09517	-.10786	-.12076	-.13392	-.14737	-.16114	-.17530	-.18988
.380	.00465	-.00763	-.01987	-.03208	-.04431	-.05658	-.06893	-.08139	-.09400	-.10677	-.11976	-.13300	-.14653	-.16039	-.17462	-.18927
.390	.00679	-.00563	-.01799	-.03033	-.04267	-.05506	-.06752	-.08008	-.09277	-.10565	-.11872	-.13205	-.14566	-.15960	-.17391	-.18865
.400	.00903	-.00354	-.01604	-.02851	-.04098	-.05348	-.06604	-.07871	-.09151	-.10447	-.11764	-.13106	-.14476	-.15878	-.17318	-.18800
.410	.01137	-.00136	-.01401	-.02661	-.03921	-.05183	-.06451	-.07728	-.09019	-.10325	-.11652	-.13003	-.14382	-.15793	-.17241	-.18732
.420	.01381	-.00091	-.01389	-.02664	-.03937	-.05211	-.06491	-.07780	-.09081	-.10398	-.11735	-.13096	-.14484	-.15904	-.17362	-.18862
.430	.01634	-.00328	-.01668	-.02958	-.04255	-.05558	-.06872	-.08200	-.09541	-.10897	-.12278	-.13684	-.15115	-.16573	-.18059	-.19588
.440	.01899	-.00575	-.02038	-.03344	-.04664	-.05998	-.07346	-.08707	-.10081	-.11470	-.12884	-.14323	-.15787	-.17276	-.18790	-.20338
.450	.02175	-.00832	-.02499	-.03821	-.05158	-.06510	-.07877	-.09258	-.10653	-.12072	-.13526	-.15005	-.16509	-.18038	-.19592	-.21171
.460	.02463	-.01099	-.02868	-.04254	-.05661	-.07089	-.08538	-.09999	-.11482	-.12987	-.14526	-.16090	-.17679	-.19293	-.20932	-.22596
.470	.02763	-.01378	-.03253	-.04668	-.06104	-.07561	-.09038	-.10536	-.12055	-.13605	-.15186	-.16798	-.18441	-.20115	-.21819	-.23553
.480	.03076	-.01669	-.03644	-.05080	-.06536	-.08013	-.09502	-.11002	-.12522	-.14063	-.15634	-.17236	-.18868	-.20531	-.22224	-.23946
.490	.03402	-.01972	-.04037	-.05492	-.06967	-.08462	-.09977	-.11512	-.13067	-.14642	-.16237	-.17852	-.19487	-.21152	-.22846	-.24568
.500	.03743	-.02288	-.04453	-.05928	-.07423	-.08938	-.10473	-.12028	-.13603	-.15198	-.16813	-.18448	-.20103	-.21778	-.23482	-.25215
.510	.04098	-.02618	-.04783	-.06258	-.07753	-.09268	-.10803	-.12358	-.13933	-.15528	-.17143	-.18778	-.20433	-.22108	-.23812	-.25545
.520	.04469	-.02962	-.05137	-.06612	-.08107	-.09622	-.11147	-.12692	-.14257	-.15842	-.17447	-.19072	-.20717	-.22382	-.24067	-.25781
.530	.04857	-.03321	-.05496	-.06971	-.08466	-.09981	-.11516	-.13071	-.14646	-.16241	-.17856	-.19491	-.21146	-.22821	-.24516	-.26230
.540	.05261	-.03695	-.05860	-.07335	-.08830	-.10345	-.11880	-.13435	-.15010	-.16605	-.18220	-.19855	-.21510	-.23185	-.24880	-.26594
.550	.05684	-.04086	-.06251	-.07726	-.09221	-.10736	-.12271	-.13826	-.15401	-.16996	-.18611	-.20246	-.21901	-.23576	-.25271	-.26985
.560	.06127	-.04495	-.06662	-.08137	-.09642	-.11167	-.12712	-.14277	-.15862	-.17467	-.19092	-.20737	-.22402	-.24087	-.25792	-.27516
.570	.06589	-.04921	-.07088	-.08563	-.10068	-.11593	-.13138	-.14703	-.16288	-.17893	-.19518	-.21163	-.22828	-.24513	-.26218	-.27942
.580	.07073	-.05367	-.07534	-.09009	-.10514	-.12039	-.13584	-.15149	-.16734	-.18339	-.19954	-.21589	-.23244	-.24919	-.26614	-.28328
.590	.07580	-.05834	-.08001	-.09476	-.10981	-.12506	-.14051	-.15616	-.17201	-.18806	-.20431	-.22076	-.23741	-.25426	-.27131	-.28855
.600	.08111	-.06322	-.08489	-.10064	-.11669	-.13304	-.14959	-.16634	-.18329	-.20044	-.21779	-.23534	-.25309	-.27104	-.28919	-.30754
.610	.08668	-.06834	-.09001	-.10576	-.12181	-.13816	-.15471	-.17146	-.18841	-.20556	-.22291	-.24046	-.25821	-.27616	-.29431	-.31266
.620	.09252	-.07369	-.09536	-.11111	-.12716	-.14351	-.16006	-.17681	-.19376	-.21091	-.22826	-.24581	-.26356	-.28151	-.29976	-.31821
.630	.09865	-.07931	-.10108	-.11683	-.13288	-.14923	-.16578	-.18253	-.19948	-.21663	-.23398	-.25153	-.26928	-.28723	-.30548	-.32393
.640	.10509	-.08520	-.10707	-.12282	-.13887	-.15522	-.17177	-.18852	-.20547	-.22262	-.23997	-.25752	-.27527	-.29322	-.31147	-.32992
.650	.11186	-.09138	-.11326	-.12901	-.14506	-.16141	-.17796	-.19471	-.21166	-.22881	-.24616	-.26371	-.28146	-.29941	-.31766	-.33611
.660	.11898	-.09788	-.11976	-.13551	-.15156	-.16791	-.18446	-.20121	-.21816	-.23531	-.25266	-.27021	-.28796	-.30591	-.32416	-.34261
.670	.12648	-.10471	-.12659	-.14234	-.15839	-.17474	-.19129	-.20804	-.22499	-.24214	-.25949	-.27704	-.29479	-.31274	-.33099	-.34944
.680	.13439	-.11190	-.13381	-.14956	-.16561	-.18196	-.19851	-.21526	-.23221	-.24936	-.26671	-.28426	-.30201	-.31996	-.33821	-.35666
.690	.14274	-.11948	-.14140	-.15715	-.17320	-.18955	-.20610	-.22285	-.23980	-.25695	-.27430	-.29185	-.30960	-.32755	-.34570	-.36405
.700	.15155	-.12746	-.14938	-.16513	-.18118	-.19753	-.21408	-.23083	-.24778	-.26493	-.28228	-.29983	-.31758	-.33553	-.35378	-.37223
.710	.16088	-.13589	-.15781	-.17356	-.18961	-.20596	-.22251	-.23926	-.25621	-.27336	-.29071	-.30826	-.32601	-.34396	-.36211	-.38046
.720	.17075	-.14479	-.16671	-.18246	-.19851	-.21486	-.23141	-.24816	-.26511	-.28226	-.29961	-.31716	-.33491	-.35286	-.37101	-.38936
.730	.18122	-.15421	-.17613	-.19188	-.20793	-.22428	-.24083	-.25758	-.27453	-.29168	-.30903	-.32658	-.34433	-.36228	-.38043	-.39878
.740	.19234	-.16419	-.18611	-.20186	-.21791	-.23426	-.25081	-.26756	-.28451	-.30166	-.31891	-.33636	-.35391	-.37166	-.38961	-.40776
.750	.20416	-.17477	-.19669	-.21244	-.22849	-.24484	-.26139	-.27814	-.29509	-.31224	-.32959	-.34714	-.36489	-.38284	-.40109	-.41954
.760	.21674	-.18600	-.20792	-.22367	-.23972	-.25607	-.27262	-.28937	-.30632	-.32347	-.34082	-.35837	-.37612	-.39407	-.41222	-.43057
.770	.23017	-.19795	-.21987	-.23562	-.25167	-.26792	-.28437	-.30102	-.31787	-.33492	-.35217	-.36962	-.38727	-.40512	-.42317	-.44142
.780	.24453	-.21069	-.23261	-.24836	-.26441	-.28076	-.29731	-.31406	-.33101	-.34816	-.36551	-.38306	-.40081	-.41876	-.43691	-.45526
.790	.25990	-.22427	-.24619	-.26194	-.27799	-.29434	-.31089	-.32764	-.34459	-.36174	-.37909	-.39664	-.41439	-.43234	-.45049	-.46884

TABLE 3

M1\N2=	.060	.080	.100	.120	.140	.160	.180	.200	.220	.240	.260	.280	.300	.320	.340	.360
.300	.52265	.52282	.52338	.52432	.52565	.52736	.52947	.53198	.53490	.53825	.54205	.54631	.55105	.55630	.56209	.56845
.310	.52421	.52432	.52481	.52569	.52696	.52895	.53069	.53316	.53605	.53937	.54314	.54737	.55209	.55732	.56309	.56943
.320	.52584	.52587	.52630	.52712	.52834	.52995	.53196	.53439	.53724	.54053	.54426	.54847	.55316	.55837	.56413	.57046
.330	.52754	.52750	.52786	.52861	.52976	.53132	.53329	.53567	.53849	.54173	.54544	.54961	.55428	.55947	.56521	.57152
.340	.52931	.52919	.52947	.53016	.53125	.53275	.53467	.53701	.53978	.54299	.54666	.55080	.55545	.56061	.56633	.57263
.350	.53116	.53095	.53115	.53177	.53280	.53424	.53610	.53839	.54112	.54429	.54792	.55204	.55665	.56179	.56749	.57377
.360	.53308	.53278	.53290	.53345	.53441	.53579	.53759	.53983	.54251	.54564	.54923	.55331	.55790	.56302	.56869	.57496
.370	.53507	.53468	.53473	.53520	.53608	.53734	.53914	.54132	.54395	.54704	.55059	.55464	.55920	.56428	.56994	.57618
.380	.53717	.53662	.53662	.53700	.53782	.53906	.54075	.54287	.54545	.54849	.55200	.55601	.56054	.56560	.57123	.57745
.390	.53934	.53874	.53859	.53888	.53962	.54079	.54241	.54448	.54700	.54999	.55347	.55744	.56192	.56696	.57256	.57877
.400	.54160	.54089	.54064	.54084	.54149	.54259	.54414	.54614	.54861	.55155	.55498	.55891	.56336	.56836	.57394	.58013
.410	.54394	.54312	.54276	.54287	.54344	.54445	.54593	.54787	.55028	.55316	.55654	.56043	.56485	.56982	.57537	.58153
.420	.54639	.54544	.54498	.54498	.54545	.54639	.54779	.54966	.55200	.55483	.55816	.56201	.56639	.57132	.57684	.58298
.430	.54893	.54786	.54727	.54717	.54754	.54839	.54971	.55151	.55379	.55656	.55984	.56364	.56797	.57287	.57837	.58448
.440	.55157	.55036	.54966	.54944	.54972	.55047	.55171	.55343	.55564	.55835	.56158	.56532	.56962	.57448	.57994	.58603
.450	.55433	.55297	.55213	.55180	.55197	.55263	.55378	.55542	.55756	.56020	.56337	.56707	.57131	.57614	.58156	.58762
.460	.55719	.55568	.55470	.55425	.55430	.55486	.55592	.55748	.55954	.56212	.56522	.56887	.57307	.57785	.58324	.58927
.470	.56016	.55850	.55738	.55679	.55673	.55718	.55814	.55961	.56159	.56410	.56714	.57073	.57488	.57962	.58497	.59097
.480	.56326	.56142	.56015	.55943	.55924	.55958	.56043	.56181	.56372	.56615	.56912	.57265	.57675	.58144	.58676	.59273
.490	.56648	.56447	.56304	.56217	.56185	.56206	.56281	.56410	.56591	.56827	.57117	.57464	.57868	.58333	.58860	.59454
.500	.56983	.56763	.56603	.56501	.56455	.56464	.56528	.56646	.56819	.57046	.57329	.57669	.58067	.58527	.59050	.59640
.510	.57332	.57092	.56914	.56796	.56735	.56732	.56784	.56891	.57054	.57272	.57548	.57881	.58278	.58728	.59246	.59832
.520	.57696	.57435	.57238	.57102	.57026	.57009	.57048	.57144	.57297	.57506	.57774	.58099	.58486	.58935	.59449	.60031
.530	.58074	.57791	.57574	.57421	.57328	.57296	.57322	.57407	.57549	.57749	.58007	.58326	.58705	.59148	.59657	.60235
.540	.58469	.58162	.57924	.57751	.57642	.57594	.57607	.57678	.57809	.57999	.58249	.58559	.58932	.59369	.59872	.60446
.550	.58880	.58548	.58287	.58094	.57967	.57903	.57901	.57960	.58079	.58258	.58498	.58800	.59165	.59596	.60094	.60663
.560	.59308	.58950	.58665	.58451	.58305	.58224	.58206	.58251	.58358	.58526	.58756	.59049	.59407	.59830	.60323	.60887
.570	.59756	.59369	.59059	.58823	.58656	.58557	.58523	.58553	.58646	.58803	.59023	.59307	.59656	.60072	.60559	.61118
.580	.60222	.59805	.59469	.59209	.59020	.58902	.58851	.58866	.58945	.59089	.59298	.59572	.59913	.60322	.60802	.61355
.590	.60710	.60261	.59896	.59610	.59399	.59260	.59191	.59190	.59255	.59386	.59583	.59847	.60179	.60580	.61053	.61601
.600	.61219	.60736	.60341	.60028	.59793	.59633	.59544	.59526	.59575	.59693	.59878	.60131	.60453	.60846	.61312	.61853
.610	.61751	.61232	.60804	.60463	.60203	.60020	.59911	.59874	.59907	.60010	.60183	.60424	.60736	.61120	.61579	.62114
.620	.62308	.61750	.61288	.60916	.60629	.60422	.60291	.60235	.60251	.60339	.60498	.60727	.61029	.61404	.61854	.62382
.630	.62891	.62291	.61793	.61389	.61072	.60839	.60686	.60610	.60608	.60680	.60824	.61041	.61331	.61696	.62138	.62659
.640	.63502	.62858	.62320	.61881	.61534	.61274	.61097	.60999	.60978	.61032	.61161	.61365	.61643	.61998	.62431	.62945
.650	.64142	.63450	.62871	.62395	.62015	.61727	.61523	.61403	.61361	.61398	.61511	.61700	.61966	.62310	.62734	.63240
.660	.64815	.64071	.63447	.62931	.62517	.62197	.61967	.61822	.61759	.61776	.61873	.62047	.62300	.62632	.63046	.63543
.670	.65521	.64722	.64049	.63492	.63041	.62688	.62429	.62258	.62172	.62169	.62247	.62406	.62645	.62965	.63368	.63857
.680	.66263	.65405	.64681	.64078	.63587	.63199	.62909	.62711	.62601	.62577	.62636	.62778	.63002	.63309	.63701	.64180
.690	.67044	.66122	.65342	.64691	.64158	.63733	.63409	.63182	.63047	.62999	.63038	.63162	.63371	.63665	.64045	.64514
.700	.67876	.66876	.66036	.65333	.64754	.64289	.63931	.63672	.63510	.63438	.63456	.63561	.63753	.64033	.64400	.64859
.710	.68735	.67669	.66765	.66006	.65378	.64870	.64474	.64183	.63991	.63894	.63889	.63974	.64149	.64413	.64768	.65215
.720	.69652	.68504	.67531	.66711	.66031	.65478	.65042	.64715	.64492	.64367	.64338	.64402	.64558	.64806	.65147	.65582
.730	.70622	.69386	.68337	.67452	.66713	.66113	.65634	.65270	.65013	.64860	.64805	.64846	.64983	.65214	.65540	.65962
.740	.71649	.70317	.69185	.68230	.67433	.66778	.66253	.65848	.65556	.65372	.65290	.65307	.65423	.65635	.65945	.66355
.750	.72738	.71301	.70081	.69049	.68186	.67474	.66900	.66452	.66122	.65905	.65794	.65786	.65879	.66072	.66366	.66760
.760	.73896	.72344	.71026	.69912	.68978	.68205	.67577	.67083	.66703	.66460	.66318	.66283	.66352	.66525	.66800	.67180
.770	.75127	.73451	.72026	.70822	.69811	.68971	.68286	.67742	.67329	.67038	.66894	.66899	.66943	.67094	.67351	.67714
.780	.76441	.74625	.73085	.71783	.70688	.69777	.69030	.68433	.67973	.67641	.67431	.67336	.67353	.67481	.67717	.68063
.790	.77846	.75876	.74208	.72799	.71613	.70624	.69810	.69156	.68646	.68271	.68022	.67894	.67883	.67985	.68201	.68529

TABLE 4

TABLE OF D = (FO-1)*F2 - F1**2

M1\M2=	.060	.080	.100	.120	.140	.160	.180	.200	.220	.240	.260	.280	.300	.320	.340	.360
.300	.02390	.02368	.02349	.02333	.02319	.02308	.02298	.02291	.02287	.02285	.02285	.02288	.02293	.02300	.02311	.02324
.310	.02568	.02544	.02523	.02505	.02490	.02477	.02467	.02459	.02454	.02452	.02452	.02454	.02460	.02468	.02479	.02492
.320	.02753	.02729	.02705	.02685	.02668	.02654	.02643	.02635	.02629	.02626	.02626	.02628	.02634	.02642	.02654	.02668
.330	.02947	.02924	.02899	.02873	.02855	.02841	.02827	.02818	.02811	.02808	.02807	.02810	.02815	.02824	.02836	.02852
.340	.03150	.03119	.03092	.03069	.03049	.03032	.03018	.03008	.03001	.02997	.02996	.02999	.03004	.03013	.03026	.03042
.350	.03361	.03328	.03299	.03273	.03251	.03233	.03218	.03207	.03199	.03194	.03193	.03195	.03201	.03210	.03224	.03241
.360	.03582	.03546	.03514	.03486	.03463	.03442	.03426	.03413	.03404	.03399	.03398	.03400	.03406	.03415	.03429	.03447
.370	.03813	.03774	.03739	.03709	.03682	.03661	.03643	.03629	.03619	.03613	.03610	.03612	.03618	.03628	.03643	.03662
.380	.04053	.04011	.03973	.03940	.03912	.03888	.03868	.03853	.03841	.03835	.03832	.03834	.03839	.03850	.03865	.03885
.390	.04304	.04258	.04217	.04181	.04150	.04124	.04102	.04086	.04073	.04065	.04062	.04063	.04069	.04080	.04095	.04116
.400	.04565	.04515	.04471	.04432	.04398	.04370	.04346	.04328	.04314	.04305	.04301	.04302	.04308	.04319	.04335	.04356
.410	.04838	.04784	.04736	.04693	.04657	.04626	.04600	.04580	.04565	.04555	.04550	.04550	.04556	.04567	.04583	.04606
.420	.05122	.05063	.05011	.04965	.04926	.04892	.04864	.04842	.04825	.04814	.04808	.04808	.04813	.04824	.04841	.04864
.430	.05418	.05355	.05298	.05249	.05206	.05169	.05138	.05114	.05095	.05083	.05076	.05075	.05080	.05091	.05109	.05133
.440	.05727	.05658	.05597	.05544	.05497	.05457	.05424	.05397	.05376	.05362	.05354	.05353	.05357	.05369	.05387	.05411
.450	.06049	.05975	.05909	.05851	.05800	.05757	.05720	.05691	.05668	.05652	.05643	.05641	.05645	.05656	.05675	.05700
.460	.06385	.06305	.06233	.06170	.06115	.06068	.06029	.05996	.05972	.05954	.05943	.05940	.05944	.05955	.05973	.06000
.470	.06730	.06648	.06571	.06503	.06443	.06392	.06349	.06314	.06287	.06267	.06255	.06250	.06254	.06264	.06283	.06310
.480	.07100	.07006	.06923	.06849	.06784	.06729	.06682	.06644	.06614	.06592	.06578	.06572	.06574	.06585	.06604	.06632
.490	.07482	.07380	.07289	.07209	.07140	.07079	.07028	.06987	.06954	.06929	.06913	.06906	.06908	.06918	.06937	.06965
.500	.07879	.07769	.07671	.07585	.07509	.07444	.07389	.07343	.07307	.07280	.07262	.07253	.07253	.07263	.07282	.07311
.510	.08294	.08175	.08069	.07976	.07894	.07823	.07763	.07713	.07673	.07643	.07623	.07613	.07612	.07621	.07640	.07670
.520	.08727	.08599	.08484	.08383	.08294	.08218	.08152	.08098	.08054	.08021	.07999	.07986	.07984	.07992	.08011	.08041
.530	.09179	.09040	.08917	.08807	.08711	.08628	.08544	.08471	.08408	.08344	.08318	.08304	.08300	.08308	.08327	.08347
.540	.09652	.09502	.09368	.09250	.09146	.09056	.08979	.08914	.08862	.08822	.08793	.08776	.08771	.08777	.08795	.08826
.550	.10146	.09983	.09839	.09711	.09598	.09501	.09417	.09347	.09290	.09245	.09213	.09194	.09186	.09191	.09209	.09240
.560	.10662	.10486	.10330	.10192	.10070	.09964	.09873	.09797	.09734	.09685	.09650	.09627	.09618	.09621	.09639	.09669
.570	.11202	.11012	.10843	.10693	.10561	.10447	.10348	.10265	.10197	.10143	.10103	.10077	.10065	.10068	.10084	.10115
.580	.11767	.11562	.11379	.11217	.11074	.10950	.10843	.10752	.10678	.10618	.10574	.10545	.10530	.10531	.10546	.10576
.590	.12359	.12137	.11939	.11763	.11609	.11474	.11358	.11259	.11178	.11113	.11064	.11030	.11013	.11011	.11025	.11055
.600	.12979	.12738	.12524	.12334	.12167	.12021	.11894	.11787	.11698	.11627	.11573	.11535	.11514	.11510	.11523	.11552
.610	.13629	.13368	.13136	.12930	.12749	.12591	.12454	.12337	.12240	.12162	.12102	.12060	.12035	.12028	.12039	.12068
.620	.14314	.14028	.13777	.13554	.13358	.13186	.13037	.12911	.12805	.12719	.12652	.12605	.12576	.12566	.12575	.12603
.630	.15027	.14720	.14448	.14206	.13993	.13807	.13646	.13508	.13393	.13298	.13225	.13172	.13139	.13125	.13132	.13159
.640	.15779	.15446	.15151	.14889	.14658	.14456	.14281	.14131	.14005	.13902	.13821	.13762	.13723	.13706	.13710	.13736
.650	.16570	.16209	.15888	.15604	.15354	.15135	.14944	.14781	.14644	.14531	.14441	.14375	.14331	.14310	.14335	.14365
.660	.17403	.17010	.16661	.16353	.16082	.15844	.15637	.15460	.15310	.15186	.15088	.15014	.14964	.14938	.14956	.14987
.670	.18279	.17852	.17474	.17139	.16844	.16586	.16361	.16168	.16005	.15870	.15761	.15679	.15623	.15591	.15585	.15604
.680	.19204	.18739	.18327	.17964	.17643	.17363	.17119	.16909	.16730	.16582	.16463	.16372	.16308	.16271	.16260	.16277
.690	.20179	.19672	.19225	.18830	.18482	.18177	.17911	.17683	.17488	.17326	.17195	.17094	.17022	.16978	.16963	.16976
.700	.21209	.20657	.20170	.19740	.19361	.19030	.18741	.18492	.18280	.18103	.17959	.17847	.17766	.17715	.17694	.17704
.710	.22299	.21697	.21166	.20697	.20286	.19925	.19611	.19340	.19108	.18915	.18756	.18632	.18541	.18482	.18456	.18466
.720	.23454	.22795	.22216	.21706	.21257	.20865	.20523	.20227	.19975	.19763	.19589	.19452	.19350	.19282	.19249	.19249
.730	.24678	.23958	.23325	.22768	.22280	.21852	.21479	.21157	.20882	.20650	.20459	.20307	.20193	.20116	.20075	.20070
.740	.25979	.25189	.24497	.23889	.23357	.22890	.22484	.22133	.21832	.21579	.21369	.21201	.21074	.20986	.20937	.20926
.750	.27361	.26496	.25738	.25074	.24492	.23983	.23540	.23157	.22829	.22551	.22321	.22136	.21994	.21894	.21836	.21818
.760	.28840	.27863	.27053	.26326	.25690	.25135	.24651	.24233	.23874	.23570	.23317	.23113	.22956	.22843	.22774	.22748
.770	.30406	.29360	.28448	.27652	.26956	.26349	.25821	.25364	.24972	.24639	.24362	.24136	.23961	.23834	.23753	.23719
.780	.32087	.30933	.29933	.29057	.28295	.27631	.27054	.26554	.26125	.25761	.25456	.25208	.25013	.24870	.24777	.24732
.790	.33887	.32612	.31508	.30549	.29713	.28986	.28354	.27808	.27338	.26939	.26604	.26331	.26115	.25954	.25846	.25791

TABLE 5

TABLE OF SQRT(1 + F2/D)

M1\N2=	.060	.080	.100	.120	.140	.160	.180	.200	.220	.240	.260	.280	.300	.320	.340	.360
.300	4.78209	4.80361	4.82457	4.84495	4.86479	4.88406	4.90278	4.92094	4.93853	4.95560	4.97212	4.98806	5.00344	5.01826	5.03250	5.04617
.310	4.62784	4.64867	4.66893	4.68865	4.70784	4.72649	4.74459	4.76215	4.77919	4.79569	4.81166	4.82710	4.84196	4.85629	4.87008	4.88328
.320	4.48320	4.50338	4.52303	4.54211	4.56071	4.57878	4.59634	4.61331	4.62980	4.64577	4.66115	4.67619	4.69058	4.70445	4.71781	4.73060
.330	4.34375	4.36291	4.38156	4.40046	4.42247	4.43998	4.45700	4.47346	4.48946	4.50496	4.51995	4.53443	4.54838	4.56183	4.57475	4.58714
.340	4.21949	4.23846	4.25694	4.27492	4.29240	4.30939	4.32588	4.34188	4.35738	4.37242	4.38696	4.40100	4.41453	4.42758	4.44011	4.45215
.350	4.09893	4.11735	4.13532	4.15276	4.16974	4.18624	4.20226	4.21779	4.23285	4.24744	4.26157	4.27520	4.28834	4.30101	4.31318	4.32486
.360	3.98507	4.00298	4.02043	4.03740	4.05390	4.06993	4.08549	4.10059	4.11524	4.12941	4.14314	4.15638	4.16915	4.18145	4.19328	4.20462
.370	3.87736	3.89478	3.91175	3.92826	3.94431	3.95991	3.97506	3.98974	4.00397	4.01776	4.03111	4.04399	4.05640	4.06837	4.07987	4.09098
.380	3.77532	3.79229	3.80881	3.82488	3.84050	3.85568	3.87043	3.88472	3.89858	3.91199	3.92497	3.93751	3.94959	3.96123	3.97241	3.98313
.390	3.67851	3.69505	3.71113	3.72679	3.74201	3.75680	3.77115	3.78507	3.79857	3.81164	3.82428	3.83648	3.84825	3.85958	3.87047	3.88090
.400	3.58654	3.60266	3.61835	3.63361	3.64844	3.66286	3.67685	3.69041	3.70356	3.71630	3.72861	3.74051	3.75196	3.76301	3.77361	3.78377
.410	3.49906	3.51479	3.53009	3.54497	3.55944	3.57350	3.58714	3.60037	3.61320	3.62562	3.63762	3.64922	3.66039	3.67115	3.68149	3.69140
.420	3.41575	3.43110	3.44603	3.46055	3.47467	3.48839	3.50171	3.51462	3.52713	3.53924	3.55096	3.56227	3.57317	3.58367	3.59375	3.60342
.430	3.33631	3.35130	3.36588	3.38006	3.39385	3.40724	3.42024	3.43284	3.44506	3.45689	3.46832	3.47936	3.49000	3.50025	3.51008	3.51951
.440	3.26048	3.27513	3.28937	3.30323	3.31670	3.32978	3.34248	3.35480	3.36673	3.37828	3.38944	3.40022	3.41061	3.42062	3.43022	3.43943
.450	3.18802	3.20234	3.21627	3.22981	3.24298	3.25576	3.26818	3.28021	3.29187	3.30315	3.31407	3.32460	3.33475	3.34452	3.35390	3.36289
.460	3.11871	3.13272	3.14634	3.15958	3.17246	3.18496	3.19710	3.20887	3.22027	3.23130	3.24197	3.25226	3.26218	3.27173	3.28090	3.28969
.470	3.05235	3.06605	3.07939	3.09234	3.10494	3.11717	3.12905	3.14056	3.15171	3.16250	3.17293	3.18300	3.19270	3.20204	3.21101	3.21959
.480	2.98876	3.00217	3.01522	3.02791	3.04024	3.05221	3.06383	3.07509	3.08601	3.09657	3.10677	3.11663	3.12611	3.13525	3.14402	3.15241
.490	2.92776	2.94090	2.95368	2.96610	2.97817	2.98990	3.00127	3.01230	3.02299	3.03332	3.04331	3.05296	3.06225	3.07118	3.07977	3.08798
.500	2.86920	2.88207	2.89459	2.90676	2.91859	2.93008	2.94122	2.95202	2.96248	2.97261	2.98239	2.99183	3.00092	3.00968	3.01807	3.02611
.510	2.81294	2.82555	2.83783	2.84975	2.86134	2.87260	2.88352	2.89410	2.90435	2.91427	2.92386	2.93311	2.94201	2.95058	2.95881	2.96667
.520	2.75884	2.77121	2.78324	2.79494	2.80630	2.81733	2.82804	2.83841	2.84845	2.85818	2.86757	2.87663	2.88536	2.89375	2.90181	2.90952
.530	2.70679	2.71892	2.73072	2.74219	2.75333	2.76414	2.77465	2.78482	2.79467	2.80420	2.81341	2.82229	2.83084	2.83907	2.84696	2.85452
.540	2.65665	2.66856	2.68014	2.69139	2.70233	2.71294	2.72323	2.73321	2.74287	2.75222	2.76125	2.76996	2.77834	2.78641	2.79414	2.80155
.550	2.60835	2.62003	2.63140	2.64244	2.65317	2.66359	2.67369	2.68348	2.69296	2.70213	2.71098	2.71953	2.72775	2.73566	2.74324	2.75050
.560	2.56176	2.57324	2.58440	2.59524	2.60577	2.61600	2.62591	2.63552	2.64482	2.65382	2.66251	2.67089	2.67896	2.68672	2.69416	2.70128
.570	2.51682	2.52809	2.53905	2.54970	2.56008	2.57008	2.57981	2.58925	2.59838	2.60721	2.61574	2.62397	2.63188	2.63950	2.64680	2.65378
.580	2.47342	2.48449	2.49526	2.50572	2.51588	2.52574	2.53530	2.54456	2.55353	2.56221	2.57058	2.57865	2.58643	2.59390	2.60106	2.60791
.590	2.43149	2.44238	2.45296	2.46323	2.47322	2.48290	2.49230	2.50140	2.51021	2.51872	2.52692	2.53488	2.54258	2.54994	2.55687	2.56360
.600	2.39096	2.40166	2.41206	2.42216	2.43198	2.44150	2.45073	2.45967	2.46832	2.47669	2.48477	2.49256	2.50005	2.50725	2.51416	2.52076
.610	2.35176	2.36228	2.37251	2.38244	2.39209	2.40145	2.41052	2.41931	2.42781	2.43603	2.44397	2.45162	2.45899	2.46606	2.47284	2.47932
.620	2.31383	2.32418	2.33423	2.34400	2.35348	2.36268	2.37161	2.38024	2.38860	2.39669	2.40449	2.41201	2.41924	2.42619	2.43285	2.43922
.630	2.27710	2.28728	2.29717	2.30678	2.31610	2.32515	2.33393	2.34242	2.35064	2.35859	2.36626	2.37365	2.38076	2.38759	2.39413	2.40038
.640	2.24151	2.25153	2.26126	2.27072	2.27989	2.28880	2.29743	2.30578	2.31382	2.32168	2.32922	2.33648	2.34347	2.35019	2.35661	2.36276
.650	2.20702	2.21688	2.22646	2.23576	2.24480	2.25356	2.26205	2.27026	2.27820	2.28589	2.29322	2.30046	2.30733	2.31393	2.32025	2.32629
.660	2.17357	2.18329	2.19272	2.20187	2.21076	2.21938	2.22774	2.23582	2.24365	2.25121	2.25850	2.26553	2.27229	2.27878	2.28499	2.29092
.670	2.14113	2.15069	2.15998	2.16899	2.17774	2.18623	2.19445	2.20241	2.21011	2.21755	2.22473	2.23164	2.23829	2.24466	2.25077	2.25661
.680	2.10964	2.11905	2.12820	2.13708	2.14569	2.15405	2.16214	2.16998	2.17756	2.18488	2.19194	2.19874	2.20528	2.21155	2.21756	2.22330
.690	2.07906	2.08833	2.09734	2.10609	2.11457	2.12280	2.13077	2.13848	2.14595	2.15315	2.16010	2.16680	2.17323	2.17940	2.18551	2.19095
.700	2.04935	2.05849	2.06737	2.07598	2.08434	2.09244	2.10029	2.10789	2.11524	2.12233	2.12917	2.13576	2.14209	2.14817	2.15398	2.15952
.710	2.02048	2.02949	2.03824	2.04672	2.05496	2.06294	2.07067	2.07815	2.08539	2.09237	2.09911	2.10560	2.11183	2.11781	2.12352	2.12898
.720	1.99241	2.00129	2.00991	2.01828	2.02639	2.03426	2.04187	2.04925	2.05637	2.06325	2.06988	2.07629	2.08240	2.08829	2.09391	2.09928
.730	1.96512	1.97387	1.98237	1.99061	1.99861	2.00636	2.01386	2.02113	2.02814	2.03492	2.04145	2.04774	2.05378	2.05957	2.06511	2.07039
.740	1.93855	1.94719	1.95556	1.96369	1.97157	1.97921	1.98661	1.99376	2.00068	2.00736	2.01379	2.01998	2.02593	2.03163	2.03708	2.04228
.750	1.91270	1.92121	1.92947	1.93749	1.94526	1.95279	1.96008	1.96713	1.97395	1.98052	1.98686	1.99296	1.99882	2.00443	2.00980	2.01492
.760	1.88753	1.89592	1.90407	1.91197	1.91964	1.92706	1.93420	1.94120	1.94791	1.95440	1.96064	1.96665	1.97242	1.97795	1.98323	1.98827
.770	1.86301	1.87129	1.87931	1.88712	1.89468	1.90200	1.90909	1.91594	1.92256	1.92894	1.93510	1.94102	1.94670	1.95215	1.95735	1.96231
.780	1.83912	1.84729	1.85522	1.86291	1.87036	1.87758	1.88457	1.89132	1.89784	1.90414	1.91021	1.91604	1.92164	1.92700	1.93213	1.93701
.790	1.81583	1.82390	1.83172	1.83930	1.84666	1.85378	1.86067	1.86733	1.87376	1.87997	1.88595	1.89169	1.89721	1.90249	1.90754	1.91234

TABLE 6

TABLE OF SQRT(FD)/(FD - 1)

M1\N2=	.060	.080	.100	.120	.140	.160	.180	.200	.220	.240	.260	.280	.300	.320	.340	.360
.300	4.77329	4.76155	4.72517	4.66587	4.58628	4.48951	4.37901	4.25819	4.13024	3.99802	3.86392	3.72991	3.59752	3.46793	3.34197	3.22021
.310	4.62223	4.61577	4.58448	4.53574	4.46573	4.37913	4.27894	4.16822	4.04994	3.92673	3.80090	3.67437	3.54867	3.42500	3.30428	3.18709
.320	4.47994	4.47804	4.45000	4.41185	4.35044	4.27302	4.18227	4.08089	3.97159	3.85684	3.73824	3.61944	3.50016	3.38224	3.26660	3.15390
.330	4.34572	4.34776	4.33020	4.29381	4.24010	4.17103	4.08889	3.99613	3.89517	3.78838	3.67778	3.56518	3.45207	3.33969	3.22898	3.12065
.340	4.21889	4.22435	4.21162	4.18126	4.13448	4.07298	3.99869	3.91386	3.82070	3.72336	3.61776	3.51162	3.40443	3.29739	3.19147	3.08742
.350	4.09883	4.10739	4.09883	4.07383	4.03329	3.97861	3.91157	3.83407	3.74815	3.65579	3.55880	3.45883	3.35729	3.25540	3.15412	3.05423
.360	3.98505	3.99612	3.99142	3.97122	3.93629	3.88784	3.82739	3.75666	3.67750	3.59167	3.50093	3.40680	3.31068	3.21374	3.11696	3.02111
.370	3.87704	3.89038	3.88903	3.87311	3.84326	3.80048	3.74609	3.68161	3.60870	3.52901	3.44416	3.35559	3.26464	3.17246	3.08002	2.98810
.380	3.77438	3.78973	3.79133	3.77925	3.75398	3.71635	3.66752	3.60881	3.54174	3.46779	3.38849	3.30520	3.21919	3.13159	3.04333	2.95523
.390	3.67668	3.69377	3.69800	3.68937	3.66825	3.63532	3.59158	3.53882	3.47656	3.40801	3.33393	3.25565	3.17436	3.09114	3.00693	2.92252
.400	3.58359	3.60220	3.60878	3.60324	3.58587	3.55723	3.51817	3.46974	3.41313	3.34963	3.28049	3.20695	3.13015	3.05145	2.97084	2.89001
.410	3.49478	3.51473	3.52339	3.52064	3.50667	3.48195	3.44718	3.40332	3.35142	3.29264	3.22816	3.15912	3.08661	3.01164	2.93508	2.85772
.420	3.40996	3.43107	3.44159	3.44135	3.43047	3.40932	3.37853	3.33889	3.29137	3.23702	3.17692	3.11214	3.04372	2.97262	2.89967	2.82566
.430	3.32883	3.35099	3.36317	3.36519	3.35712	3.33925	3.31210	3.27637	3.23293	3.18274	3.12677	3.06604	3.00151	2.93440	2.86463	2.79386
.440	3.25122	3.27426	3.28792	3.29199	3.28648	3.27160	3.24781	3.21572	3.17608	3.12977	3.07770	3.02079	2.95997	2.89610	2.82998	2.76233
.450	3.17685	3.20066	3.21565	3.22157	3.21838	3.20426	3.18557	3.15684	3.12075	3.07808	3.02968	2.97640	2.91911	2.85862	2.79572	2.73108
.460	3.10552	3.13002	3.14620	3.15378	3.15272	3.14312	3.12529	3.09968	3.06690	3.02765	2.98271	2.93287	2.87893	2.82168	2.76186	2.70014
.470	3.03705	3.06215	3.07939	3.08848	3.08936	3.08207	3.06688	3.04418	3.01449	2.97845	2.93677	2.89018	2.83943	2.78528	2.72842	2.66951
.480	2.97126	2.99888	3.01507	3.02554	3.02819	3.02304	3.01028	2.99027	2.96347	2.93044	2.89183	2.84832	2.80062	2.74943	2.69541	2.63920
.490	2.90799	2.93407	2.95311	2.96483	2.96909	2.96590	2.95541	2.93790	2.91379	2.88359	2.84787	2.80729	2.76248	2.71411	2.66283	2.60922
.500	2.84710	2.87357	2.89338	2.90623	2.91198	2.91059	2.90219	2.88701	2.86541	2.83786	2.80489	2.76707	2.72501	2.67935	2.63068	2.57958
.510	2.78845	2.81526	2.83572	2.84963	2.85702	2.85702	2.85055	2.83754	2.81830	2.79325	2.76285	2.72765	2.68821	2.64512	2.59896	2.55028
.520	2.73190	2.75901	2.78102	2.79494	2.80329	2.80510	2.80043	2.78944	2.77241	2.74969	2.72173	2.68901	2.65207	2.61144	2.56769	2.52193
.530	2.67735	2.70472	2.72638	2.74204	2.75154	2.75477	2.75177	2.74267	2.72710	2.70718	2.68151	2.65115	2.61657	2.57831	2.53686	2.49273
.540	2.62467	2.65226	2.67442	2.69087	2.70141	2.70595	2.70450	2.69716	2.68412	2.66567	2.64218	2.61404	2.58172	2.54570	2.50646	2.46449
.550	2.57378	2.60156	2.62416	2.64132	2.65283	2.65859	2.65857	2.65287	2.64164	2.62514	2.60370	2.57768	2.54751	2.51363	2.47651	2.43661
.560	2.52457	2.55251	2.57552	2.59332	2.60572	2.61260	2.61393	2.60975	2.60022	2.58556	2.56605	2.54203	2.51391	2.48209	2.44700	2.40909
.570	2.47696	2.50504	2.52841	2.54680	2.56002	2.56874	2.57052	2.56777	2.55984	2.54690	2.52922	2.50711	2.48093	2.45106	2.41793	2.38193
.580	2.43086	2.45905	2.48275	2.50169	2.51567	2.52455	2.52828	2.52688	2.52044	2.50914	2.49318	2.47288	2.44855	2.42055	2.38929	2.35512
.590	2.38619	2.41449	2.43848	2.45791	2.47259	2.48237	2.48719	2.48704	2.48201	2.47223	2.45792	2.43933	2.41676	2.39055	2.36107	2.32868
.600	2.34289	2.37127	2.39552	2.41541	2.43074	2.44135	2.44718	2.44821	2.44450	2.43617	2.42340	2.40644	2.38555	2.36105	2.33329	2.30260
.610	2.30089	2.32933	2.35383	2.37413	2.39005	2.40144	2.40822	2.41035	2.40788	2.40092	2.38962	2.37420	2.35491	2.33205	2.30592	2.27687
.620	2.26011	2.28861	2.31332	2.33402	2.35049	2.36260	2.37026	2.37342	2.37212	2.36645	2.35654	2.34259	2.32483	2.30353	2.27898	2.25149
.630	2.22050	2.24905	2.27396	2.29501	2.31200	2.32478	2.33327	2.33740	2.33721	2.33275	2.32446	2.31160	2.29529	2.27548	2.25244	2.22647
.640	2.18200	2.21059	2.23569	2.25706	2.27453	2.28794	2.29720	2.30225	2.30309	2.29979	2.29245	2.28122	2.26659	2.24971	2.22632	2.20180
.650	2.14457	2.17319	2.19845	2.22013	2.23804	2.25204	2.26202	2.26793	2.26976	2.26755	2.26139	2.25142	2.23781	2.22079	2.20059	2.17748
.660	2.10814	2.13679	2.16220	2.18416	2.20249	2.21704	2.22771	2.23442	2.23717	2.23599	2.23096	2.22219	2.20985	2.19413	2.17526	2.15348
.670	2.07267	2.10135	2.12690	2.14912	2.16784	2.18291	2.19421	2.20169	2.20532	2.20511	2.20114	2.19352	2.18238	2.16791	2.15032	2.12983
.680	2.03812	2.06682	2.09250	2.11497	2.13405	2.14960	2.16151	2.16970	2.17416	2.17488	2.17193	2.16539	2.15540	2.14213	2.12576	2.10652
.690	2.00444	2.03316	2.05897	2.08166	2.10108	2.11709	2.12957	2.13844	2.14368	2.14528	2.14329	2.13779	2.12890	2.11677	2.10158	2.08353
.700	1.97159	2.00034	2.02626	2.04917	2.06891	2.08533	2.09836	2.10788	2.11386	2.11629	2.11522	2.11071	2.10286	2.09183	2.07777	2.06087
.710	1.93954	1.96830	1.99433	2.01745	2.03750	2.05433	2.06786	2.07798	2.08466	2.08809	2.08879	2.08670	2.08252	2.07532	2.06532	2.05283
.720	1.90824	1.93703	1.96316	1.98647	1.99681	2.00403	2.00803	2.00974	2.00946	2.00707	2.00260	2.00583	2.00241	2.00312	2.00123	2.00165
.730	1.87765	1.90647	1.93271	1.95621	1.97682	1.99440	2.00886	2.02011	2.02809	2.03279	2.03422	2.03241	2.02745	2.01943	2.00850	1.99479
.740	1.84776	1.87661	1.90295	1.92663	1.94749	1.96543	1.98032	1.99209	2.00067	2.00606	2.00823	2.00725	2.00316	1.99608	1.98610	1.97339
.750	1.81852	1.84741	1.87385	1.89770	1.91881	1.93708	1.95238	1.96464	1.97381	1.97984	1.98274	1.98254	1.97950	1.97309	1.96404	1.95228
.760	1.78990	1.81883	1.84537	1.86939	1.89075	1.90933	1.92503	1.93776	1.94747	1.95442	1.95972	1.96287	1.96383	1.96204	1.95822	1.95147
.770	1.76187	1.79085	1.81750	1.84168	1.86327	1.88215	1.89823	1.91141	1.92165	1.92890	1.93315	1.93442	1.93275	1.92822	1.92092	1.91095
.780	1.73440	1.76344	1.79020	1.81454	1.83636	1.85553	1.87197	1.88559	1.89632	1.90414	1.90902	1.91098	1.91006	1.90631	1.89983	1.89072
.790	1.70747	1.73658	1.76345	1.78795	1.80999	1.82945	1.84623	1.86026	1.87148	1.87984	1.88533	1.88795	1.88774	1.88475	1.87906	1.87077

TABLE 7

TABLE OF (1 + F1**2/(D*F0))**(-.5)

M1\N2=	.060	.080	.100	.120	.140	.160	.180	.200	.220	.240	.260	.280	.300	.320	.340	.360
.300	.99816	.99124	.97940	.96304	.94275	.91922	.89317	.86532	.83633	.80677	.77712	.74777	.71901	.69106	.66408	.63815
.310	.99879	.99292	.98234	.96739	.94857	.92651	.90186	.87528	.84741	.81880	.78994	.76120	.73290	.70527	.67848	.65265
.320	.99927	.99437	.98496	.97132	.95390	.93243	.90922	.88459	.85783	.83093	.80411	.77802	.75290	.72809	.70340	.66670
.330	.99963	.99561	.98729	.97488	.95876	.93922	.91741	.89329	.86763	.84093	.81568	.79125	.76797	.74509	.72250	.68031
.340	.99986	.99667	.98935	.97809	.96321	.94514	.92436	.90142	.87683	.85110	.82666	.79972	.77474	.75077	.72783	.68347
.350	.99998	.99756	.99118	.98099	.96728	.95040	.93082	.90902	.88549	.86070	.83509	.80904	.78289	.75689	.73127	.70620
.360	.99999	.99829	.99278	.98361	.97099	.95526	.93682	.91613	.89363	.86978	.84499	.81966	.79409	.76857	.74332	.71852
.370	.99992	.99887	.99419	.98596	.97438	.95974	.94240	.92277	.90128	.87835	.85439	.82977	.80481	.77979	.75493	.73043
.380	.99975	.99932	.99541	.98807	.97747	.96386	.94757	.92898	.90847	.88645	.86332	.83941	.81507	.79056	.76612	.74194
.390	.99950	.99966	.99646	.98996	.98029	.96766	.95238	.93478	.91523	.89411	.87178	.84860	.82488	.80090	.77689	.75305
.400	.99918	.99987	.99735	.99164	.98285	.97116	.95684	.94020	.92158	.90133	.87981	.85736	.83427	.81083	.78727	.76379
.410	.99878	.99998	.99810	.99314	.98517	.97438	.96098	.94527	.92755	.90816	.88744	.86570	.84325	.82035	.79725	.77416
.420	.99830	.99999	.99871	.99445	.98728	.97733	.96482	.95000	.93316	.91461	.89467	.87364	.85183	.82949	.80687	.78416
.430	.99776	.99991	.99919	.99560	.98918	.98005	.96838	.95442	.93843	.92069	.90152	.88121	.86003	.83825	.81612	.79382
.440	.99716	.99974	.99956	.99660	.99089	.98253	.97168	.95854	.94337	.92644	.90802	.88841	.86787	.84666	.82501	.80314
.450	.99650	.99948	.99981	.99745	.99242	.98479	.97472	.96239	.94802	.93186	.91419	.89527	.87536	.85472	.83357	.81212
.460	.99577	.99914	.99995	.99816	.99378	.98686	.97754	.96597	.95237	.93698	.92003	.90179	.88252	.86244	.84180	.82079
.470	.99499	.99873	1.00000	.99875	.99498	.98874	.98033	.96931	.95646	.94180	.92557	.90800	.88935	.86985	.84971	.82915
.480	.99415	.99824	.99995	.99822	.99404	.98744	.98252	.97242	.96029	.94635	.93081	.91391	.89588	.87694	.85731	.83720
.490	.99325	.99768	.99981	.99957	.99695	.99197	.98472	.97530	.96388	.95064	.93578	.91953	.90211	.88374	.86462	.84496
.500	.99230	.99705	.99958	.99982	.99773	.99335	.98673	.97798	.96723	.95467	.94048	.92487	.90806	.89024	.87164	.85244
.510	.99129	.99636	.99927	.99996	.99839	.99458	.98857	.98046	.97037	.95847	.94493	.92995	.91373	.89648	.87838	.85964
.520	.99023	.99560	.99888	1.00000	.99893	.99566	.99024	.98275	.97303	.96204	.94914	.93478	.91915	.90244	.88486	.86658
.530	.98912	.99478	.99841	.99995	.99935	.99661	.99175	.98486	.97603	.96542	.95312	.93936	.92431	.90815	.89108	.87326
.540	.98796	.99389	.99787	.99980	.99966	.99743	.99312	.98681	.97858	.96855	.95688	.94371	.92923	.91361	.89704	.87969
.550	.98675	.99295	.99725	.99957	.99987	.99812	.99435	.98859	.98094	.97151	.96042	.94784	.93392	.91884	.90277	.88588
.560	.98548	.99194	.99656	.99926	.99998	.99870	.99544	.99022	.98314	.97428	.96377	.95176	.93839	.92384	.90826	.89183
.570	.98416	.99088	.99581	.99887	.99999	.99917	.99640	.99174	.98517	.97687	.96692	.95547	.94264	.92861	.91353	.89756
.580	.98279	.98976	.99499	.99839	.99991	.99953	.99723	.99305	.98704	.97929	.96989	.95898	.94669	.93317	.91858	.90307
.590	.98137	.98858	.99410	.99784	.99975	.99978	.99775	.99426	.98877	.98154	.97268	.96231	.95054	.93753	.92342	.90836
.600	.97989	.98734	.99314	.99721	.99949	.99994	.99855	.99534	.99035	.98364	.97530	.96545	.95420	.94169	.92806	.91345
.610	.97837	.98605	.99213	.99651	.99915	1.00000	.99904	.99630	.99179	.98558	.97776	.96842	.95768	.94566	.93250	.91834
.620	.97678	.98470	.99104	.99574	.99873	.99996	.99943	.99713	.99310	.98739	.98006	.97122	.96097	.94944	.93675	.92304
.630	.97515	.98329	.98990	.99490	.99823	.99984	.99972	.99786	.99428	.98905	.98221	.97386	.96410	.95305	.94082	.92755
.640	.97345	.98182	.98869	.99399	.99765	.99963	.99990	.99847	.99534	.99057	.98421	.97635	.96710	.95648	.94471	.93188
.650	.97170	.98029	.98742	.99301	.99699	.99933	.99999	.99897	.99629	.99197	.98608	.97868	.96987	.95975	.94843	.93603
.660	.96989	.97871	.98508	.99196	.99626	.99894	.99999	.99937	.99711	.99324	.98780	.98087	.97252	.96285	.95198	.94001
.670	.96803	.97706	.98469	.99084	.99545	.99848	.99989	.99967	.99783	.99439	.98940	.98292	.97502	.96581	.95537	.94382
.680	.96610	.97535	.98323	.98965	.99457	.99793	.99971	.99987	.99844	.99542	.99087	.98483	.97738	.96861	.95860	.94747
.690	.96411	.97358	.98170	.98840	.99362	.99731	.99944	.99998	.99894	.99635	.99222	.98661	.97960	.97126	.96169	.95097
.700	.96206	.97175	.98011	.98708	.99260	.99661	.99908	.99999	.99935	.99715	.99345	.98827	.98169	.97378	.96462	.95432
.710	.95994	.96985	.97846	.98570	.99150	.99583	.99864	.99992	.99965	.99786	.99456	.98980	.98364	.97615	.96741	.95752
.720	.95775	.96789	.97674	.98424	.99033	.99497	.99812	.99975	.99986	.99846	.99556	.99122	.98547	.97840	.97007	.96057
.730	.95549	.96586	.97495	.98272	.98910	.99404	.99752	.99950	.99997	.99895	.99645	.99251	.98718	.98051	.97259	.96349
.740	.95316	.96376	.97310	.98112	.98779	.99304	.99683	.99916	1.00000	.99935	.99724	.99370	.98876	.98250	.97497	.96627
.750	.95076	.96158	.97117	.97946	.98640	.99195	.99607	.99873	.99993	.99965	.99792	.99477	.99023	.98436	.97723	.96891
.760	.94827	.95934	.96910	.97773	.98495	.99080	.99523	.99823	.99977	.99986	.99851	.99574	.99159	.98611	.97937	.97144
.770	.94571	.95701	.96710	.97592	.98342	.98957	.99431	.99764	.99953	.99997	.99899	.99660	.99283	.98774	.98139	.97383
.780	.94306	.95461	.96495	.97404	.98182	.98826	.99332	.99697	.99920	1.00000	.99938	.99736	.99397	.98926	.98359	.97610
.790	.94032	.95213	.96273	.97208	.98015	.98688	.99224	.99622	.99967	.99993	.99967	.99802	.99501	.99067	.98507	.97826

TABLE 8

TABLE OF SQR(F2/D)

M1\M2=	.060	.080	.100	.120	.140	.160	.180	.200	.220	.240	.260	.280	.300	.320	.340	.360
.300	4.67636	4.69837	4.71980	4.74063	4.76090	4.78059	4.79974	4.81826	4.83623	4.85366	4.87052	4.88679	4.90248	4.91761	4.93215	4.94609
.310	4.51850	4.53984	4.56059	4.58077	4.60041	4.61949	4.63801	4.65597	4.67339	4.69027	4.70659	4.72238	4.73758	4.75221	4.76631	4.77979
.320	4.37025	4.39095	4.41110	4.43067	4.44973	4.46822	4.48621	4.50362	4.52052	4.53687	4.55272	4.56801	4.58275	4.59694	4.61061	4.62370
.330	4.23078	4.25081	4.27043	4.28944	4.30793	4.32591	4.34337	4.36029	4.37667	4.39257	4.40794	4.42278	4.43709	4.45087	4.46412	4.47681
.340	4.09928	4.11881	4.13782	4.15631	4.17429	4.19176	4.20874	4.22515	4.24108	4.25653	4.27147	4.28587	4.29977	4.31317	4.32603	4.33839
.350	3.97507	3.99407	4.01258	4.03056	4.04805	4.06504	4.08155	4.09753	4.11303	4.12805	4.14258	4.15661	4.17012	4.18314	4.19566	4.20766
.360	3.85756	3.87606	3.89408	3.91159	3.92863	3.94516	3.96121	3.97679	3.99189	4.00650	4.02064	4.03429	4.04744	4.06011	4.07230	4.08397
.370	3.74618	3.76421	3.78177	3.79885	3.81544	3.83157	3.84722	3.86239	3.87709	3.89133	3.90511	3.91840	3.93121	3.94355	3.95541	3.96677
.380	3.64047	3.65807	3.67519	3.69184	3.70803	3.72374	3.73901	3.75380	3.76814	3.78202	3.79544	3.80841	3.82090	3.83293	3.84449	3.85555
.390	3.53997	3.55716	3.57387	3.59012	3.60591	3.62126	3.63615	3.65058	3.66458	3.67812	3.69122	3.70386	3.71605	3.72778	3.73905	3.74985
.400	3.44431	3.46109	3.47742	3.49329	3.50872	3.52371	3.53825	3.55235	3.56600	3.57923	3.59204	3.60436	3.61625	3.62770	3.63870	3.64924
.410	3.35313	3.36953	3.38549	3.40100	3.41608	3.43073	3.44493	3.45871	3.47206	3.48498	3.49747	3.50953	3.52114	3.53233	3.54307	3.55337
.420	3.26609	3.28214	3.29775	3.31292	3.32766	3.34198	3.35589	3.36936	3.38240	3.39503	3.40724	3.41903	3.43038	3.44132	3.45182	3.46188
.430	3.18292	3.19863	3.21390	3.22875	3.24318	3.25719	3.27079	3.28396	3.29673	3.30909	3.32103	3.33256	3.34367	3.35436	3.36462	3.37446
.440	3.10334	3.11873	3.13368	3.14823	3.16236	3.17607	3.18939	3.20229	3.21479	3.22688	3.23857	3.24985	3.26072	3.27118	3.28122	3.29085
.450	3.02712	3.04220	3.05686	3.07110	3.08495	3.09839	3.11143	3.12406	3.13630	3.14815	3.15960	3.17084	3.18128	3.19152	3.20135	3.21077
.460	2.95404	2.96882	2.98320	2.99715	3.01073	3.02390	3.03668	3.04907	3.06107	3.07267	3.08389	3.09471	3.10513	3.11516	3.12479	3.13401
.470	2.88390	2.89839	2.91250	2.92619	2.93950	2.95242	2.96495	2.97710	2.98885	3.00024	3.01123	3.02184	3.03205	3.04189	3.05132	3.06035
.480	2.81650	2.83073	2.84457	2.85801	2.87107	2.88375	2.89604	2.90795	2.91950	2.93065	2.94143	2.95184	2.96185	2.97149	2.98075	2.98960
.490	2.75168	2.76566	2.77925	2.79245	2.80526	2.81771	2.82978	2.84147	2.85280	2.86375	2.87433	2.88453	2.89437	2.90382	2.91290	2.92157
.500	2.68930	2.70302	2.71637	2.72933	2.74193	2.75415	2.76600	2.77749	2.78860	2.79935	2.80975	2.81976	2.82941	2.83869	2.84759	2.85611
.510	2.62919	2.64268	2.65580	2.66854	2.68091	2.69292	2.70457	2.71585	2.72677	2.73733	2.74753	2.75737	2.76685	2.77595	2.78470	2.79305
.520	2.57122	2.58449	2.59739	2.60992	2.62208	2.63388	2.64533	2.65642	2.66715	2.67753	2.68754	2.69729	2.70678	2.71591	2.72466	2.73302
.530	2.51529	2.52834	2.54103	2.55335	2.56531	2.57692	2.58818	2.59908	2.60963	2.61984	2.62969	2.63919	2.64833	2.65713	2.66556	2.67362
.540	2.46126	2.47411	2.48659	2.49872	2.51049	2.52191	2.53298	2.54371	2.55409	2.56412	2.57381	2.58315	2.59214	2.60078	2.60906	2.61699
.550	2.40904	2.42169	2.43398	2.44592	2.45750	2.46874	2.47964	2.49019	2.50040	2.51028	2.51981	2.52900	2.53784	2.54634	2.55448	2.56227
.560	2.35852	2.37098	2.38309	2.39484	2.40625	2.41732	2.42805	2.43844	2.44849	2.45820	2.46758	2.47662	2.48532	2.49369	2.50170	2.50936
.570	2.30963	2.32190	2.33383	2.34541	2.35665	2.36755	2.37812	2.38835	2.39824	2.40781	2.41704	2.42594	2.43450	2.44273	2.45062	2.45816
.580	2.26226	2.27436	2.28612	2.29755	2.30866	2.31935	2.32975	2.33983	2.34958	2.35900	2.36809	2.37686	2.38529	2.39339	2.40115	2.40857
.590	2.21634	2.22827	2.23986	2.25112	2.26203	2.27262	2.28288	2.29281	2.30242	2.31170	2.32066	2.32929	2.33760	2.34557	2.35321	2.36051
.600	2.17180	2.18357	2.19500	2.20610	2.21687	2.22731	2.23742	2.24721	2.25668	2.26583	2.27466	2.28317	2.29135	2.29920	2.30673	2.31392
.610	2.12857	2.14018	2.15147	2.16244	2.17303	2.18333	2.19331	2.20296	2.21230	2.22132	2.23002	2.23840	2.24647	2.25421	2.26162	2.26871
.620	2.08658	2.09804	2.10918	2.11998	2.13047	2.14063	2.15047	2.15999	2.16920	2.17810	2.18668	2.19494	2.20289	2.21052	2.21783	2.22481
.630	2.04577	2.05709	2.06809	2.07875	2.08910	2.09913	2.10884	2.11824	2.12733	2.13610	2.14457	2.15272	2.16056	2.16808	2.17528	2.18216
.640	2.00608	2.01727	2.02813	2.03866	2.04888	2.05878	2.06837	2.07765	2.08662	2.09528	2.10363	2.11167	2.11940	2.12682	2.13392	2.14071
.650	1.96747	1.97852	1.98925	1.99966	2.00975	2.01953	2.02900	2.03816	2.04702	2.05557	2.06381	2.07174	2.07937	2.08669	2.09370	2.10038
.660	1.92988	1.94081	1.95141	1.96169	1.97167	1.98133	1.99068	1.99973	2.00847	2.01691	2.02505	2.03289	2.04041	2.04764	2.05455	2.06115
.670	1.89326	1.90407	1.91455	1.92471	1.93457	1.94412	1.95336	1.96230	1.97094	1.97927	1.98731	1.99505	2.00248	2.00961	2.01643	2.02294
.680	1.85757	1.86826	1.87862	1.88868	1.89842	1.90786	1.91699	1.92583	1.93436	1.94260	1.95054	1.95818	1.96552	1.97255	1.97929	1.98571
.690	1.82277	1.83334	1.84360	1.85354	1.86317	1.87250	1.88154	1.89027	1.89870	1.90684	1.91469	1.92224	1.92949	1.93644	1.94309	1.94943
.700	1.78881	1.79927	1.80942	1.81926	1.82879	1.83802	1.84695	1.85559	1.86393	1.87197	1.87973	1.88719	1.89435	1.90121	1.90778	1.91404
.710	1.75566	1.76602	1.77606	1.78580	1.79523	1.80436	1.81319	1.82172	1.82996	1.83794	1.84561	1.85298	1.86004	1.86684	1.87333	1.87951
.720	1.72329	1.73354	1.74349	1.75312	1.76246	1.77150	1.78024	1.78869	1.79684	1.80472	1.81230	1.81958	1.82658	1.83329	1.83969	1.84580
.730	1.69165	1.70181	1.71166	1.72120	1.73044	1.73939	1.74804	1.75640	1.76447	1.77226	1.77976	1.78697	1.79388	1.80051	1.80684	1.81288
.740	1.66072	1.67079	1.68054	1.69000	1.69915	1.70800	1.71657	1.72485	1.73284	1.74054	1.74796	1.75509	1.76193	1.76848	1.77474	1.78071
.750	1.63047	1.64044	1.65011	1.65948	1.66854	1.67732	1.68580	1.69399	1.70190	1.70952	1.71686	1.72392	1.73069	1.73717	1.74336	1.74925
.760	1.60086	1.61075	1.62034	1.62961	1.63860	1.64729	1.65569	1.66381	1.67164	1.67919	1.68645	1.69343	1.70013	1.70654	1.71266	1.71849
.770	1.57188	1.58168	1.59119	1.60038	1.60929	1.61790	1.62622	1.63426	1.64202	1.64949	1.65669	1.66360	1.67022	1.67657	1.68262	1.68839
.780	1.54349	1.55321	1.56264	1.57176	1.58058	1.58912	1.59737	1.60533	1.61302	1.62042	1.62754	1.63439	1.64095	1.64722	1.65321	1.65891
.790	1.51567	1.52532	1.53466	1.54371	1.55246	1.56092	1.56910	1.57699	1.58461	1.59194	1.59900	1.60577	1.61227	1.61848	1.62441	1.63005

TABLE 9

TABLE OF SQR(T((FO - 1)/(D*M1**2))

M1\N2=	.060	.080	.100	.120	.140	.160	.180	.200	.220	.240	.260	.280	.300	.320	.340	.360
.300	4.61966	4.65259	4.70896	4.78843	4.89033	5.01370	5.15738	5.32006	5.50036	5.69689	5.90827	6.13315	6.37027	6.61848	6.87667	7.14385
.310	4.46105	4.48825	4.53685	4.60662	4.69703	4.80728	4.93640	5.08324	5.24662	5.42529	5.61799	5.82354	6.04076	6.26859	6.50601	6.75206
.320	4.31276	4.33501	4.37682	4.43809	4.51838	4.61704	4.73325	4.86602	5.01431	5.17700	5.35299	5.54148	5.74051	5.94998	6.16868	6.39569
.330	4.17379	4.19171	4.22760	4.28140	4.35276	4.44115	4.54588	4.66610	4.80089	4.94927	5.11024	5.28282	5.46601	5.65892	5.86068	6.07044
.340	4.04326	4.05743	4.08812	4.13532	4.19877	4.27817	4.37454	4.48815	4.60889	4.73925	4.88720	5.04257	5.20429	5.37222	5.54662	5.72726
.350	3.92041	3.93129	3.95741	3.99878	4.05521	4.12636	4.21171	4.31066	4.42248	4.54642	4.68166	4.82740	4.98281	5.14713	5.31960	5.49951
.360	3.80453	3.81257	3.83466	3.87086	3.92104	3.98493	4.06209	4.15201	4.25405	4.36752	4.49172	4.62590	4.76923	4.92128	5.08107	5.24802
.370	3.69509	3.70061	3.71913	3.75074	3.79535	3.85274	3.92256	4.00433	4.09754	4.20156	4.31575	4.43944	4.57198	4.71265	4.86085	5.01595
.380	3.59150	3.59481	3.61018	3.63771	3.67734	3.72890	3.79210	3.86653	3.95176	4.04720	4.15230	4.26645	4.38903	4.51943	4.65705	4.80132
.390	3.49332	3.49468	3.50725	3.53113	3.56630	3.61262	3.66986	3.73768	3.81565	3.90331	4.00013	4.10558	4.21908	4.34007	4.46800	4.60233
.400	3.40009	3.39975	3.40983	3.43045	3.46162	3.50323	3.55508	3.61689	3.68829	3.76887	3.85815	3.95565	4.06084	4.17321	4.29226	4.41747
.410	3.31145	3.30961	3.31748	3.33518	3.36275	3.40010	3.44709	3.50365	3.56888	3.64300	3.72539	3.81562	3.91320	4.01767	4.12854	4.24536
.420	3.22705	3.22389	3.22979	3.24488	3.26920	3.30271	3.34528	3.39669	3.45688	3.52491	3.60100	3.68457	3.77516	3.87236	3.97572	4.08480
.430	3.14659	3.14226	3.14640	3.15915	3.18055	3.21058	3.24914	3.29604	3.35106	3.41391	3.48423	3.56168	3.64586	3.73637	3.83279	3.93474
.440	3.06979	3.06443	3.06700	3.07763	3.09639	3.12327	3.15818	3.20098	3.25147	3.30938	3.37441	3.44624	3.52451	3.60885	3.69888	3.79423
.450	2.99637	2.99011	2.99128	3.00001	3.01639	3.04040	3.07200	3.11105	3.15738	3.21077	3.27094	3.33761	3.41043	3.48907	3.57319	3.66244
.460	2.92614	2.91908	2.91899	2.92601	2.94022	2.96163	2.99020	3.02583	3.06836	3.11760	3.17330	3.23520	3.30299	3.37638	3.45503	3.53861
.470	2.85886	2.85109	2.84989	2.85536	2.86761	2.88666	2.91247	2.94496	2.98400	3.02942	3.08101	3.13881	3.20166	3.27018	3.34376	3.42209
.480	2.79434	2.78596	2.78375	2.78784	2.79830	2.81519	2.83847	2.86809	2.90393	2.94584	2.99363	3.04707	3.10593	3.16993	3.23881	3.31227
.490	2.73240	2.72349	2.72038	2.72321	2.73206	2.74698	2.76795	2.79494	2.82783	2.86651	2.91079	2.96048	3.01536	3.07518	3.13969	3.20862
.500	2.67290	2.66352	2.65961	2.66130	2.66868	2.68180	2.70066	2.72522	2.75541	2.79109	2.83214	2.87835	2.92954	2.98548	3.04593	3.11044
.510	2.61568	2.60588	2.60125	2.60191	2.60795	2.61943	2.63636	2.65869	2.68638	2.71931	2.75736	2.80036	2.84812	2.90045	2.95712	3.01790
.520	2.56058	2.55043	2.54516	2.54490	2.54972	2.55970	2.57485	2.59514	2.62052	2.65091	2.68618	2.72619	2.77077	2.81974	2.87289	2.93001
.530	2.50751	2.49705	2.49121	2.49010	2.49382	2.50242	2.51594	2.53434	2.55762	2.58563	2.61833	2.65557	2.69719	2.74303	2.79220	2.84460
.540	2.45632	2.44560	2.43925	2.43739	2.44010	2.44744	2.45945	2.47612	2.49741	2.52326	2.55358	2.58824	2.62712	2.67004	2.71684	2.76734
.550	2.40693	2.39598	2.38918	2.38663	2.38842	2.39462	2.40525	2.42031	2.43979	2.46362	2.49172	2.52399	2.56029	2.60050	2.64444	2.69195
.560	2.35922	2.34809	2.34088	2.33772	2.33867	2.34381	2.35317	2.36675	2.38455	2.40650	2.43255	2.46258	2.49650	2.53417	2.57544	2.62014
.570	2.31309	2.30181	2.29426	2.29053	2.29072	2.29486	2.30308	2.31531	2.33154	2.35176	2.37589	2.40385	2.43554	2.47083	2.50960	2.55168
.580	2.26849	2.25708	2.24921	2.24498	2.24448	2.24776	2.25487	2.26583	2.28063	2.29923	2.32158	2.34760	2.37721	2.41029	2.44671	2.48634
.590	2.22529	2.21379	2.20565	2.20097	2.19983	2.20230	2.20842	2.21822	2.23168	2.24878	2.26947	2.29369	2.32135	2.35225	2.38658	2.42391
.600	2.18345	2.17188	2.16350	2.15841	2.15670	2.15843	2.16364	2.17235	2.18457	2.20027	2.21942	2.24196	2.26780	2.29686	2.32903	2.36419
.610	2.14289	2.13127	2.12268	2.11723	2.11500	2.11604	2.12041	2.12812	2.13919	2.15360	2.17130	2.19227	2.21641	2.24365	2.27389	2.30702
.620	2.10354	2.09189	2.08313	2.07735	2.07464	2.07506	2.07805	2.08544	2.09544	2.10864	2.12501	2.14450	2.16705	2.19259	2.22102	2.25224
.630	2.06534	2.05368	2.04476	2.03870	2.03556	2.03541	2.03829	2.04422	2.05323	2.06530	2.08042	2.09854	2.11960	2.14354	2.17026	2.19969
.640	2.02822	2.01657	2.00754	2.00122	1.99769	1.99702	1.99923	2.00438	2.01247	2.02349	2.03744	2.05427	2.07394	2.09637	2.12150	2.14923
.650	1.99215	1.98052	1.97139	1.96485	1.96097	1.95981	1.96162	1.96584	1.97302	1.98312	1.99598	2.01160	2.02996	2.05079	2.07461	2.10073
.660	1.95705	1.94547	1.93626	1.92952	1.92533	1.92373	1.92479	1.92852	1.93496	1.94411	1.95594	1.97040	1.98756	2.00728	2.02949	2.05413
.670	1.92289	1.91137	1.90210	1.89520	1.89072	1.88872	1.88926	1.89237	1.89808	1.90637	1.91726	1.93070	1.94668	1.96514	1.98602	2.00926
.680	1.88961	1.87816	1.86886	1.86181	1.85708	1.85473	1.85480	1.85733	1.86234	1.86985	1.87985	1.89231	1.90721	1.92450	1.94413	1.96603
.690	1.85720	1.84582	1.83650	1.82933	1.82437	1.82169	1.82133	1.82333	1.82771	1.83448	1.84364	1.85518	1.86906	1.88526	1.90371	1.92435
.700	1.82558	1.81429	1.80498	1.79754	1.79254	1.78956	1.78881	1.79031	1.79410	1.80019	1.80858	1.81925	1.83218	1.84734	1.86468	1.88415
.710	1.79473	1.78354	1.77423	1.76688	1.76155	1.75831	1.75719	1.75824	1.76148	1.76693	1.77459	1.78445	1.79649	1.81068	1.82697	1.84532
.720	1.76460	1.75353	1.74425	1.73683	1.73136	1.72787	1.72643	1.72706	1.73029	1.73465	1.74133	1.75073	1.76193	1.77520	1.79031	1.80780
.730	1.73515	1.72422	1.71498	1.70753	1.70192	1.69822	1.69648	1.69672	1.69899	1.70329	1.70984	1.71803	1.72844	1.74085	1.75523	1.77153
.740	1.70637	1.69557	1.68639	1.67892	1.67320	1.66932	1.66730	1.66719	1.66903	1.67281	1.67857	1.68629	1.69596	1.70757	1.72107	1.73643
.750	1.67822	1.66756	1.65845	1.65097	1.64517	1.64112	1.63886	1.63843	1.63986	1.64317	1.64838	1.65547	1.66445	1.67529	1.68796	1.70243
.760	1.65064	1.64015	1.63113	1.62365	1.61779	1.61359	1.61111	1.61039	1.61145	1.61432	1.61901	1.62552	1.63385	1.64397	1.65586	1.66950
.770	1.62364	1.61330	1.60439	1.59694	1.59102	1.58671	1.58404	1.58304	1.58376	1.58576	1.58884	1.59406	1.60141	1.61035	1.62072	1.63256
.780	1.59716	1.58701	1.57821	1.57080	1.56485	1.55758	1.55255	1.55028	1.55041	1.55214	1.55459	1.55806	1.56260	1.56840	1.57448	1.60157
.790	1.57118	1.56123	1.55255	1.54519	1.53924	1.53473	1.53174	1.53028	1.53041	1.53214	1.53549	1.54046	1.54706	1.55528	1.56509	1.57648